

Uncertainty-Aware Capacity Calculation and Congestion Management

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Master Thesis

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Abstract

The growing share of renewable energy in Europe’s electricity system introduces forecast uncertainty that challenges the coordinated capacity calculation and congestion management process. Current deterministic methods treat forecasts as fixed inputs and address uncertainty only indirectly, risking infeasible market outcomes that can compromise operational security.

This thesis develops a modelling framework that explicitly represents the subprocesses of the flow-based process—capacity calculation, validation, market coupling, and redispatch—under both deterministic and probabilistic formulations. Two case studies are analysed: a stylised 4-node system to isolate key mechanisms, and a 50-node PyPSA-Eur network to assess results under more complex conditions.

Across both cases, the validation step emerged as the critical stage where robustness against forecast uncertainty can be introduced most effectively. Deterministic validation reduced but did not eliminate operational infeasibilities, while probabilistic validation substantially improved robustness. Higher day-ahead market costs were offset by lower redispatch needs, reducing the impact on total system costs. These results highlight the potential of uncertainty-aware methods to enhance operational security in systems dominated by renewable energy.

Zusammenfassung

Der wachsende Anteil erneuerbarer Energien in Europas Energiesystem verstärkt Prognoseunsicherheiten, die den koordinierten Prozess der Kapazitätsberechnung und des Engpassmanagements vor Herausforderungen stellen. Die derzeit angewandten Verfahren beruhen überwiegend auf deterministischen Ansätzen, welche Prognosen als feste Eingaben behandeln und Unsicherheiten indirekt über statische Sicherheitsmargen berücksichtigen. Dies kann zu nicht umsetzbaren Marktergebnissen führen, die die operationale Sicherheit gefährden.

Im Rahmen dieser Arbeit wird ein Modellierungsansatz entwickelt, der die Teilprozesse der Lastflussbasierten Marktkopplung — Kapazitätsberechnung, Validierung, Marktkopplung und Redispatch — sowohl in deterministischer als auch in probabilistischer Formulierung systematisch abbildet. Zwei Fallstudien werden untersucht: ein stilisiertes Vier-Knoten-System zur Herausarbeitung der grundlegenden Mechanismen, sowie ein 50-Knoten-Netzwerk auf Basis von PyPSA-Eur zur Analyse der Zusammenhänge unter komplexeren Bedingungen.

In beiden Untersuchungen erweist sich die Validierung als kritischer Prozessschritt, an dem robuste Verfahren gegen Prognoseunsicherheiten am effektivsten eingeführt werden können. Während die deterministische Validierung die Zahl der verbleibenden Überlastungen unter Unsicherheit nur bedingt reduziert, erhöht die probabilistische Validierung die operationale Sicherheit signifikant. Die dadurch steigenden Marktkosten werden durch einen geringeren Redispatch-Bedarf kompensiert, sodass der Effekt auf die Gesamtsystemkosten limitiert ist. Die Ergebnisse verdeutlichen den Beitrag probabilistischer Ansätze zur Stärkung der Systemsicherheit in von erneuerbaren Energien geprägten Stromsystemen.

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List of Abbreviations

AC Alternating Current

AMR Adjustment for Minimum RAM

CACM Capacity Allocation and Congestion Management

CCR Capacity Calculation Region

CGM Common Grid Model

CNE Critical Network Element

CNEC Critical Network Element and Contingency

CV Coordinated Validation

CVA Coordinated Validation Adjustment

D2CF 2-Days Ahead Congestion Forecast

DA CCM Day-Ahead Capacity Calculation Methodology

DACC Day-Ahead Capacity Calculation

EDP Economic Dispatch Problem

FBMC Flow-Based Market Coupling

FRM Flow Reliability Margin

GSK Generation Shift Key

IEM Internal Energy Market

IGM Individual Grid Model

IV Individual Validation

IVA Individual Validation Adjustment

MCP Market Clearing Point

minRAM Minimum Remaining Available Margin

MTU Market Time Unit

NEMO Nominated Electricity Market Operator

NPF Net Position Forecast

OPF Optimal Power Flow

PCR Price Coupling of Regions

PST Phase Shift Transformer

PTDF Power Transmission Distribution Factor

PV Photovoltaic

RA Remedial Action

RAM Remaining Available Margin

RAO Remedial Action Optimisation

RES Renewable Energy Sources

RO Remaining Overloads

SIDC Single Intra-Day Coupling

TSO Transmission System Operator

Introduction

1.1 Motivation

The decarbonisation of the global energy system is a key prerequisite for achieving international climate goals, such as those set out in the Paris Agreement [1]. This objective is driving a fundamental transformation of electricity systems worldwide, characterized by the expansion of Renewable Energy Sources (RES) [2], increasing electrification across sectors [3], and the planned phase-out of conventional fossil-fuel-based power plants [4]. Studies have shown that cross-zonal energy exchange is becoming increasingly important for the energy system transformation as it enables the efficient integration of variable RES [5], enhances security of supply [6], and promotes market efficiency [6, 7]. However, the transmission network required to support such exchanges evolves at a comparatively slow pace, resulting in persistently limited cross-zonal transmission capacities [8].

In this context, Transmission System Operators (TSOs) play a central role in maintaining secure system operation while enabling the efficient use of limited transmission capacity. This is achieved through the coordinated processes of Capacity Allocation and Congestion Management (CACM), which determine the amount of cross-zonal capacity that can be safely offered to the market and resolve any resulting grid congestions through preventive or curative measures [9].

However, the increasing penetration of RES presents significant challenges for these processes. Due to their temporal and spatial variability, renewable generation is to some extent uncertain [10]. The growing share of RES, combined with a largely static grid topology and the declining availability of conventional generation, reduces the operational flexibility available to TSOs. This increases the risk of unresolvable network congestions that can compromise operational security and necessitates robust, adaptive planning methods that explicitly address renewable forecast uncertainties.

Current operational practices rely predominantly on deterministic approaches, where renewable forecasts are treated as fixed inputs and uncertainty is only indirectly addressed through static safety margins [11]. As a result, forecast errors are not explicitly modelled in today's capacity allocation and congestion management procedures. This can lead either to overly conservative capacity restrictions, which limit market efficiency, or to inadequate preparation for unforeseen grid congestions, which compromise operational

security and can require costly emergency measures. Among the subprocesses of the CACM framework, capacity calculation and validation are particularly critical in this regard, as they are conducted at two days before delivery under the highest forecast uncertainty and their decisions directly impact the market outcome. The lack of explicit treatment of forecast uncertainty in these steps constitutes the central problem addressed in this thesis.

1.2 Structure of the Thesis

The thesis is structured into six chapters that progress logically from context and problem definition to methodology, application, and conclusions:

Chapter 1 – Introduction: Presents the motivation for the study and outlines the structure of the thesis.

Chapter 2 – Background & Problem Description: Provides a detailed account of the European day-ahead process chain, with a focus on capacity calculation, validation, market coupling, and redispatch. It highlights the role of forecast uncertainty and identifies gaps in current practice that motivate the modelling approach. It also reviews existing literature, defines the research problem and the research questions.

Chapter 3 – Methodology: Introduces the modelling framework developed in this thesis. It describes the mathematical formulations of the subprocesses, the treatment of renewable forecast uncertainty, and the implementation of deterministic and probabilistic approaches.

Chapter 4 – Application: Applies the framework to two case studies of increasing complexity.

The stylised **4-node system** demonstrates the basic mechanisms by which forecast uncertainty propagates through the process chain. It illustrates subprocess sensitivity to forecast errors, highlights the role of validation, and compares deterministic and probabilistic validation methods.

The **50-node system**, aggregated from a European network model, tests whether these insights persist under more complex and diverse system conditions.

Chapter 5 – Discussion and Limitations: Interprets the findings of the case studies in relation to the research questions, compares them with the literature, and reflects on methodological and practical implications. It also discusses the limitations of the modelling approach and assumptions.

Chapter 6 – Conclusions and Outlook: Summarises the main contributions of the thesis, answers the research questions, and outlines directions for future research on uncertainty-aware capacity calculation and congestion management.

Background & Problem Description

2.1 Market Coupling Processes in the European Market

The liberalization of the European electricity sector has led to the development of the Internal Energy Market (IEM), which aims to foster competition, improve efficiency, and facilitate integration across national electricity systems [2]. A fundamental design element of the IEM is the zonal market structure, whereby the European electricity market is partitioned into bidding zones. Each bidding zone is a geographical area within which internal transmission constraints are assumed to be negligible. Consequently, a uniform electricity price is determined for each Market Time Unit (MTU) within a given bidding zone.

To enable electricity trade between these zones, market coupling mechanisms are employed. Market coupling facilitates the coordinated allocation of cross-zonal transmission capacities, thereby allowing electricity to flow from regions with lower prices to those with higher prices, maximizing overall welfare [12]. However, the physical limitations of physical links between bidding zones, so-called interconnectors, impose constraints on cross-border electricity flows [8]. As a result, available transmission capacities must be both calculated in advance and allocated efficiently through coordinated processes [13].

The day-ahead market is the central element in European electricity trading, organised as a single daily auction in which electricity is traded for each hour of the following day¹. According to the European Power Exchange EPEX SPOT [15], the volume traded on the day-ahead market was 654 TWh in 2024, continuing the trend of increasing trade volumes over the last two decades. In comparison, the traded intra-day volume amounts to roughly a third (215 TWh in 2024). The day-ahead market yields market clearing prices and schedules that reflect supply and demand across the interconnected European grid. It fulfills multiple critical functions [16]: it provides the reference price for derivative markets, serves as a benchmark for regulatory authorities, and it reduces the reliance on intraday and balancing markets.

¹While the day-ahead market currently operates with hourly MTU, this will change to 15 minutes by October 2025 [14].

To ensure secure cross-zonal electricity exchange under limited network capacities, a series of processes defined under the CACM framework [9] are executed. These can be simplified into four main steps: Capacity Calculation, Validation, Market Coupling, and Congestion Management. The steps span the two days preceding electricity delivery:

Capacity Calculation (D-2) - Two days before delivery, TSOs coordinate to determine the available cross-zonal transmission capacities that can be safely offered to the market.

Validation (D-2) - These capacities are then validated by the TSOs to ensure they comply with system security requirements.

Market Coupling (D-1) - On the day before delivery, validated capacities are used in the market coupling process to match supply and demand across zones and determine zonal prices.

Congestion Management (D-0) - Starting after market coupling, any residual congestion in the grid is resolved through redispatch measures.

In reality, the operational processes are more complex. Day-ahead and intraday processes often overlap, and multiple intraday auctions, coupled with continuous trading under the Single Intra-Day Coupling (SIDC) framework, allow market participants to adjust their positions up to five minutes before delivery [17]. In parallel, redispatch actions are continuously planned and activated to resolve forecasted or real-time congestions in the network. For a comprehensive description of the processes of European market coupling, see [18].

This study focuses exclusively on the day-ahead processes, with congestion management via redispatch forming the fourth and final step following market coupling. In the following sections, each of these four process steps is described in more detail.

2.1.1 Flow-Based Capacity Calculation

The objective of the capacity calculation process is to determine the amount of cross-zonal transmission capacity that can be safely made available to the market, while maintaining secure grid operation. In the European IEM, this process is carried out in a geographically coordinated manner within so-called Capacity Calculation Regions (CCRs) [19], depicted in Fig. 2.1, which are responsible for implementing a method for the Day-Ahead Capacity Calculation (DACC) in accordance with the CACM Guideline [9] set by the European Commission.

Fig. 2.1.: Capacity Calculation Regions in Europe. Source: [12]

The CACM Guideline designates the *flow-based approach* as the primary method for capacity calculation and requires each CCR to develop a detailed implementation methodology [9]. Since 2022, the Core CCR has adopted the Flow-Based Market Coupling (FBMC) methodology as its official capacity calculation approach. The developed flow-based capacity calculation methodology is documented in the so-called "Day-Ahead Capacity Calculation Methodology (DA CCM) of the Core Capacity Calculation Region"² [20]. The main principles are outlined in the following.

At the core of the FBMC method is the calculation of the flow-based parameters on Critical Network Elements (CNEs). Network elements, typically lines or transformers, are referred to as *critical* if they are particularly sensitive to cross-zonal exchanges. The Core DA CCM states the threshold of a minimum value of 5% for the so-called zone-to-zone Power Transmission Distribution Factor (PTDF) (see 2.1.1) [20]. CNEs are assessed under N-0 and potential N-1 situations, meaning that the system must remain secure even if another element fails and are then referred to as Critical Network Element and Contingencies (CNECs).

The main output of the flow-based capacity calculation are the flow-based parameters. The flow-based parameters describe (i) how cross-zonal exchanges affect flows on transmission elements, expressed through the zonal PTDF matrix and (ii) how much capacity is available on those elements to accommodate cross-zonal exchanges, expressed through the Remaining Available Margin (RAM) on each CNEC. The combination of zonal PTDFs and RAMs results in the set of flow-based parameters that form the output of the capacity

²The most recent version is the third revised amendment published on 08.12.2023

calculation. These parameters define a feasible region of market outcomes, referred to as the flow-based domain. The flow-based domain represents all combinations of zonal net positions and zonal exchanges that are physically admissible, given the network's loading limits and its sensitivity to cross-zonal trade. The market outcome, determined in the market coupling process (Section 2.1.3), will realise as one out of all combinations of net positions and zonal exchanges inside the flow-based domain. Graphically, the domain corresponds to a multi-dimensional³ polyhedron bounded by linear inequalities, often visualised in reduced dimensions for illustration. An example two dimensional representation for three zones with exemplary market results is shown in Figure 2.2.

The parameters are determined by the TSOs prior to market clearing, with calculations beginning two days prior to the delivery day (D-2) and concluding with the auction of market coupling at 12pm of the day-ahead (D-1). As the market outcome is not known at the time of calculation, the flow-based calculation is based on a forecast predicting the state of the electricity system at the delivery moment, the so-called Common Grid Model (CGM) or 2-Days Ahead Congestion Forecast (D2CF) and also referred to as *Basecase* in the literature [21, 22]. Each TSO provides an Individual Grid Model (IGM) representing "the best possible forecast of transmission system conditions" for each MTU [9]. The line flows in the basecase are referred to as the *reference flows*, which are used to calculate the RAM. These IGMs are merged into one CGM for the CCR. The forecasted zonal net positions are referred to as Net Position Forecast (NPF).

Zonal PTDF

Zonal PTDFs describe the sensitivity of CNECs to a change in zonal net positions, the zone-to-line sensitivity. This relationship can be derived by combining the node-to-line sensitivity, expressed through the nodal PTDF and the relationship how zonal net position changes are realised at the nodal level, which is captured in the Generation Shift Keys (GSKs).

GSKs define this distribution, by specifying which generators are assumed to increase or decrease output when a zone's net position changes. Each TSO defines the GSKs for their control area given the available generation and load at the forecasted MTU [20]. GSKs are based on predictions of the market outcome, since the actual market outcome is not known yet, making them subject to forecast errors [23].

The zonal PTDFs are calculated as a weighted sum of the nodal PTDFs, with the GSKs as weights. The nodal PTDF matrix is based on the underlying network topology and can be derived as explained in Section 3.1.2.

³The number of dimensions is equivalent to the number of bidding zone borders in the CCR.

Fig. 2.2.: Example flow-based domain with minRAM enlargement. Source: Own Figure based on [24].

Remaining Available Margin

The RAM is the parameter that specifies how much capacity on a critical network element remains available for day-ahead market exchanges. With the the Regulation (EU) 2019/943 on the internal market for electricity [13] a minimum capacity margin was introduced, that has to be reserved for flows induced by cross-zonal exchange. This, so called Minimum Remaining Available Margin (minRAM) is defined to be 70% of the physical line capacity⁴ on a CNEC. The Core DA CCM [20] describes the methodology of how RAM values are calculated and how the minRAM requirement is met.

The RAM on a CNEC is calculated based on the maximum line capacity reduced by the expected flow in the delivery situation without commercial exchanges within the Core CCR and reduced by a security margin. The flows in the situation without commercial exchanges are the reference flows in the forecasted basecase situation, corrected for the flows induced by the commercial exchanges between zones in that situation. The security margin, the so-called Flow Reliability Margin (FRM) is a static safety margin used to compensate for approximations and simplifications made in the flow-based process [20]. For the mathematical formulations, see section 3.3.3. The calculated RAM values together with the zonal PTDF constitute the *initial* flow-based parameters and can be visualized in the initial domain as in Fig. 2.2. In this initial domain, the market outcome is restricted by a grid constraint, represented through a line in the two dimensional representation.

To meet minRAM requirements, the Adjustment for Minimum RAM (AMR) is introduced. If the previously calculated RAM is lower than the required threshold of 70% of the maximum capacity, the AMR is added to fulfill the requirement, artificially enlarging the trading domain [20]. With this approach, 70% of a CNEC's capacity is provided for cross-zonal trade as a lump-sum, regardless of the previously calculated parameters. It therefore relies on the idea, that a MCP that lies in the enlarged domain and outside the

⁴The physical line capacity is calculated from the maximum admissible current based on the thermal limit of a net work element [20]

previously computed initial domain (see Fig. 2.2) can be secured by *available remedial actions* in the congestion management step. Remedial Actions (RAs) are defined as "any measure applied by a TSO or several TSOs, manually or automatically, in order to maintain operational security" [9]. This includes non-costly RAs, e.g. topology changes and changing of Phase Shift Transformer (PST) taps, as well as costly RAs like redispatch measures and countertrading [25]. Redispatch is further explained in Section 2.1.4.

The availability of RAs has to be determined for each MTU by the TSOs individually. It therefore becomes evident, that if the compliance with minRAM regulation relies on the availability and application of RAs after market coupling, a validation step becomes necessary to check if the necessary RAs are available. The validation procedure following the capacity calculation ensures that the derived trading domains do not compromise system security.

2.1.2 Validation

The purpose of the validation process is to ensure that possible market outcomes resulting from the calculated flow-based domain are compatible with secure system operation. A market clearing outcome can result in remaining congestions, which under normal circumstances can be resolved through redispatch measures. However, if a particular outcome corresponds to a grid state where, including all remedial actions, no feasible solution exists to alleviate these congestions, the outcome is *not operationally secure*. As mentioned above, the application of AMRs relies on the availability of RAs, which must be checked during validation. The CACM guideline states that each TSO may reduce the available cross-zonal capacity of CNECs "for reasons of operational security" (CACM Guideline, Article 26(3) [9]), based on individual or coordinated validation. According to the Core DA CCM, TSOs should "analyse [...] whether the cross-zonal capacity could violate operational security limits, and whether they have sufficient RAs to avoid such violations" (Article 20(2) [20]). If RAs are not sufficiently available to avoid violations of operational security limits, the capacity on a CNEC can be reduced by applying a validation adjustment, thereby reducing the previously calculated RAM.

The CACM Guideline describes validation as a two-step process: the Coordinated Validation (CV) at CCR level and the Individual Validation (IV) carried out by each individual TSO[9]. In practice, only the IV has been in place since the go-live of Core DACC, while the recent amendment of the Core DA CCM specifies the future coordinated validation in more detail [26, 27]. In this process, the CV is performed first, followed by the IV, which serves as a safeguard and allows for local refinements. Accordingly, capacity reductions introduced in the coordinated step are referred to as Coordinated Validation Adjustments (CVAs), while those stemming from the individual step are called Individual Validation Adjustments (IVAs).

The main inputs of the validation are the flow-based domain based on the parameters calculated before validation, the underlying CGM used as the basecase, and the data of all available RAs. With the flow-based domain, the solution space for all possible market results is given. If the MCP were already known, only that specific situation would need to be checked for operational security violations, given the available RAs. In such a case, a flow-based domain with multiple possible market directions would not be necessary. As the MCP is not yet known, a representative set of possible market outcomes must be analysed instead. In the Core DA CCM, these outcomes are referred to as *circumstances* [26]. Their selection is guided by three principles: (i) plausibility with respect to forecasted net positions, (ii) technical feasibility regarding generation and load constraints, and (iii) extremeness in terms of being on or close to the edge of the flow-based domain [26]. Plausibility means that circumstances should resemble likely market outcomes, avoiding the analysis of purely theoretical cases. Technical feasibility ensures that the circumstances can actually occur in practice: a bidding zone cannot export more power than it can generate, nor import more than its demand.

For each selected circumstance, a Remedial Action Optimisation (RAO) is performed [26]. The RAO simulates whether the circumstance can be securely facilitated with the available RAs. If this is not possible, the domain is restricted through a CVA to exclude the infeasible outcome. A similar principle applies in the IV, where IVAs may be applied to address local issues not captured in the coordinated step.

The output of the validation process consists of a set of CVAs and IVAs, which reduce RAM on selected CNECs. These final RAM values, together with the zonal PTDF, constitute the final flow-based parameters that are used in the subsequent market coupling step.

2.1.3 Market Coupling

Market coupling is the process of efficiently utilizing the limited transmission capacity available between different countries or bidding zones and is jointly organized by the TSOs and the Nominated Electricity Market Operators (NEMOs) [28]. The central objective is, according to the CACM guideline, "*maximising economic surplus for single day-ahead coupling for the price-coupled region for the next trading day*" (Article 38(1a) [9]). This is achieved by simultaneously clearing the day-ahead market and implicitly allocating the available cross-zonal transmission capacity.

Inputs to the market coupling process are the validated cross-zonal capacity limits from the capacity calculation with validation, and the orders submitted by market participants [9]. The algorithm determines how much electricity can flow between zones while respecting capacity limits and clearing the market across all bidding zones. If no constraints are

binding, prices across the coupled zones will fully converge; otherwise, price differences persist, reflecting the scarcity of transmission capacity.

Bids and offers are matched simultaneously across all bidding zones. On the supply side, generation offers are ranked in ascending order of price, while on the demand side, consumption bids reflect the willingness to pay. The algorithm accepts bids until supply and demand are balanced in each zone. The last accepted bid — whether a generation offer or a demand bid — sets the uniform clearing price for that bidding zone. All accepted supply and demand orders in the zone are then settled at this marginal price, consistent with the CACM guideline (Article 38(1b) [9]).

In Europe, day-ahead market coupling is realised through the EUPHEMIA algorithm (Pan-European Hybrid Electricity Market Integration Algorithm), developed under the Price Coupling of Regions (PCR) project [29]. The process is implemented as a welfare-maximising optimization problem. The algorithm seeks the combination of accepted bids and allocated cross-zonal exchanges that maximises total social welfare, i.e. the sum of consumer and producer surplus plus congestion rents [29]. The main outputs of this optimisation for each bidding zone and market time unit are: (i) a single clearing price in EUR/MWh, (ii) the net position (import or export), and (iii) the information needed to determine the execution status of orders, including the accepted volumes [9].

While market coupling ensures that cross-zonal capacities are allocated efficiently and welfare is maximised in the day-ahead timeframe, the resulting net positions and cross-border exchanges can lead to congestions once the market outcome is translated into physical power flows. This is a result of simplifications in the capacity calculation process and the before mentioned minRAM enlargement (see section 2.1.1). Managing these congestions and ensuring secure system operation in real time requires the activation of remedial measures, most prominently redispatch. The following section therefore introduces the principles of congestion management and redispatch as the final step in the day-ahead process.

2.1.4 Redispatch

Physical congestions that remain after capacity calculation and allocation must be resolved by the TSOs through remedial actions such as redispatch or countertrading. Under the CACM Regulation, these measures are to be coordinated across TSOs [9]. Redispatch refers to a "*measure performed by one or several TSOs by altering specific generation and/or load patterns in order to change physical flows in the transmission system and relieve physical congestions.*" (Common Methodology for Coordinated Redispatching and Countertrading for the Core CCR Article 2, 3 [30]). The measure can be applied within a control area, bidding zone or in between bidding zones (cross-border redispatch). By reducing the

output of certain generators while simultaneously increasing the output of others, the overall active power injection into the system remains balanced, but the power flows are redirected in such a way that the congestion is alleviated [31].

Currently, redispatch is regulated on a national basis, meaning that the specific procedures and responsibilities are defined within the legal and regulatory frameworks of each member state. A coordinated approach to congestion management is currently developed in the Core CCR with the *Core TSOs' common methodology for regional operational security coordination (ROSC)* [32].

Because the power system is highly interconnected, a contingency in one area can propagate through the network and, in the worst case, trigger a large-scale blackout. In the case that congestions cannot be resolved with redispatch - resulting in Remaining Overloads (RO) - , emergency procedures within the ENTSO-E Network Codes are available, which, in extreme cases, also include load shedding.[33].

In principle, such emergency situations should be rare, since the preceding steps of capacity calculation, validation, and market coupling are designed to prevent infeasible market outcomes and minimise the need for emergency corrective measures. However, with the increasing share of variable RES and the associated forecast uncertainty, it is no longer clear whether such cases will remain exceptional, which motivates this study. In the following section, the interaction of forecast uncertainty in renewable energy production with the capacity calculation and congestion management process chain is explored.

2.2 Introduction of Forecast Uncertainty into the Process Chain

All four subprocesses of capacity calculation, validation, market coupling, and redispatch are affected by forecast uncertainty, although in different ways. The degree of uncertainty depends on the temporal distance to the time of delivery [34]. Forecasts at D-2 are less accurate than those at D-1 and D-0, while by the time of delivery uncertainty is essentially resolved. Figure 2.3 illustrates how forecast uncertainty interacts with the process chain through the inputs to each subprocess.

The inputs that depend on forecasts at each stage are

- (i) the CGM, which includes the NPF, for capacity calculation and validation at D-2
- (ii) the market orders submitted by participants for market coupling at D-1

(iii) the actual availability of power plants at D-0 for redispatch.

Since each subprocess produces outputs that serve as inputs to subsequent stages, the effects of forecast uncertainty propagate along the entire chain.

Capacity calculation is based on the CGM, a forecast of the grid situation prepared at D-2, when uncertainty is highest. Its outputs—the flow-based parameters—are highly influential because they define the feasible domain for market coupling. To account for forecast errors and modelling simplifications in FBMC (such as CNEC selection and the choice of GSKs), a fixed safety margin, the FRM, is included. Two points are important: first, FRMs are static margins based on historical data and kept constant for a given time period [27], and thus do not explicitly reflect forecast uncertainty in a given situation; second, FRMs are applied before minRAM adjustments, meaning that in cases where minRAM enlarges the domain, the safety margin is effectively overwritten.

The validation step follows a few hours after capacity calculation and relies on the CGM and forecast data at that time. While the forecasts can be updated between capacity calculation and validation, both processes rely on predictions two days in advance. In this study they are therefore assumed to have the same D-2 information available. The role of validation is to reduce the flow-based domain whenever operational security would otherwise be endangered, thereby serving as a corrective measure against infeasible market outcomes introduced earlier in the process. However, based on the limited publicly available information on the implementation of validation procedures, current practice does not explicitly account for forecast uncertainty in this step [35].

Market coupling takes place at D-1, when forecasts are more accurate than at D-2. Market participants place bids according to their own expectations of the following day, and a welfare-maximising clearing algorithm determines the market outcome. This process is not controlled by TSOs, but its outcome is limited by the flow-based domain provided through capacity calculation and validation. Thus, forecast uncertainty influences market

Fig. 2.3.: Interaction of forecast uncertainty with the process chain. Source: Own Figure

coupling directly through the behaviour of market participants and indirectly, through the market domain provided by TSOs.

Redispatch is executed at D-0, when the actual availability of generation and demand is largely known. At this stage, forecast uncertainty is minimal, and redispatch decisions are primarily based on realised values. Nevertheless, redispatch is not entirely independent of forecasts, since the dimensioning and procurement of redispatch reserves must be planned ahead of delivery. The influence of forecast errors is therefore twofold: indirectly, when redispatch must resolve congestions arising from earlier market outcomes based on imperfect forecasts; and directly, when reserve planning does not match actual system needs.

If capacity calculation and validation at D-2 do not sufficiently account for uncertainty, the resulting market outcome at D-1 may create situations that redispatch cannot fully resolve at D-0, leading to ROs. In such cases, the earlier TSO processes have not fulfilled their purpose.

In summary, while all four subprocesses are affected by forecast uncertainty to some degree, only capacity calculation and validation involve TSO decisions taken directly under uncertain conditions. Because these decisions propagate through the subsequent stages and determine both market outcomes and redispatch requirements, they represent the natural points for incorporating robustness against forecast errors.

2.3 Related Literature

The literature on FBMC can be broadly grouped into conceptual documentation, academic studies on modeling and parametrization, and more recent analyses considering the role of RES. Initial publications stem from TSO documentation [36], complemented by early evaluations such as the “dry-run” in 2008 [37] and the parallel run in 2013 [38]. The process is further described in the continuously updated Day-Ahead Capacity Calculation Methodology of the Core Capacity Calculation Region, currently available in its third amendment [20].

Academic studies subsequently turned to modeling FBMC in greater detail, with particular attention to parametrization. Several works assess the effect of generation shift keys [39, 40, 22], while others examine the impact of CNEC selection [41] and the treatment of security margins [42]. The influence of minRAM on welfare is investigated by [24] and [43]. It is found to increase trade volume, but also congestion management costs, thereby offsetting the welfare benefits of stronger market coupling. The impact on operational security is not assessed. More general modeling fundamentals are provided by [44], while

[45] present an open-source implementation. Although these studies provide valuable insights into the FBMC process and its parametrization, the integration of RES has only been addressed to a limited extent. Some scenario-based analyses include higher RES shares [43, 24], but typically under perfect forecast assumptions.

Beyond FBMC, a broader strand of research has focused on modeling uncertainty in power system operation. Early stochastic formulations represent renewable forecast errors through scenario sets and optimize expected costs, as in stochastic unit commitment and dispatch models [46]. While these approaches capture variability, they often struggle with scalability and do not guarantee feasibility across all scenarios. An alternative is chance-constrained optimization, which enforces feasibility with a specified probability. [47] introduced a tractable chance-constrained optimal power flow (CC-OPF), showing that probabilistic line limits can be enforced in large-scale grids. Building on this, [48] proposed risk- and variance-aware pricing, and [49] extended the concept to market design, integrating renewable uncertainty into price formation. These contributions demonstrate that probabilistic methods can balance operational security and economic efficiency more effectively than deterministic safety margins.

Only a few studies explicitly consider forecast uncertainty in relation to FBMC. [50] investigate the impact of generation shift key choices in different bidding zone configurations and additionally model forecast errors, finding little effect on overall system costs but without assessing operational security implications. [51] examine forecasting errors in both NTC-based and flow-based coupling and conclude that errors can lead to remaining congestions, pointing to the need for further investigation. The most recent and most closely related contribution is by [11], who propose a chance-constrained reformulation of the flow reliability margin (FRM). Their approach replaces fixed security margins with probabilistic ones, allowing renewable forecast errors to be internalised directly into the capacity calculation stage. Applied to the IEEE 118-bus system, the method reduces redispatch and congestion management costs under high shares of intermittent generation. However, their formulation does not include the validation step as a distinct subprocess. Robustness is therefore introduced only *ex ante*, at the stage of capacity calculation, whereas potential influence of minRAM adjustments is not considered.

In contrast, the present thesis extends the scope by explicitly modelling validation as an independent stage in the CACM process. This makes it possible to capture how forecast uncertainty materialises after market coupling, and to analyse how robustness can be incorporated not only during capacity calculation but also at validation. In doing so, the thesis addresses a gap left by earlier studies and provides a more complete picture of uncertainty propagation through the coordinated European capacity calculation and congestion management chain.

Taken together, the literature highlights two parallel developments: increasingly detailed modeling of FBMC and the growing use of probabilistic methods to address renewable uncertainty. Yet, these strands remain largely disconnected. FBMC studies typically model uncertainty only indirectly, for instance through deterministic sensitivities, while probabilistic methods such as chance-constrained OPF have not been applied to the CACM process chain. To date, no study has explicitly modelled the validation step or systematically examined how uncertainty propagates across capacity calculation, validation, market coupling, and redispatch. This gap provides the central motivation for the present thesis.

2.4 Problem Description

The European day-ahead process chain—capacity calculation, validation, market coupling, and redispatch—is increasingly challenged by high shares of renewable generation and associated forecast uncertainty. While flow-based market coupling (FBMC) provides a coordinated methodology for allocating scarce cross-zonal capacity, current practice remains predominantly deterministic: renewable forecasts are treated as fixed inputs, and uncertainty is only indirectly addressed through static safety margins.

The central problem is that deterministic CACM procedures fail to explicitly account for renewable forecast uncertainty, especially at D–2 and D–1 when errors are largest. As a result, cross-zonal capacity may be over-allocated, leading to infeasible market outcomes, increased redispatch needs, and compromised operational security. Although these challenges are recognised, there is limited systematic research on how uncertainty propagates through the full process chain. In particular, the *validation step*, which acts as a safeguard between capacity calculation and market coupling, has received little attention despite its critical role in determining whether uncertain outcomes can be secured with available remedial actions.

To address this gap, this thesis develops a modelling framework that explicitly captures the propagation of renewable forecast uncertainty across the day-ahead process chain, with particular attention to the validation step. The framework enables systematic comparison of deterministic and probabilistic approaches and their implications for both market efficiency and system security. The novelty of this work lies in integrating the validation step into an uncertainty-aware representation of FBMC and in testing robustness across ensembles of scenarios.

The overarching research question is:

How does renewable forecast uncertainty affect the processes of capacity calculation, validation, market coupling, and redispatch in flow-based market coupling, and how can robustness be incorporated into these processes?

To address this, three sub-questions are investigated:

RQ1: Which subprocesses are most affected by renewable forecast uncertainty, and thus most relevant for integrating uncertainty into decision making?

RQ2: How do deterministic approaches perform when renewable forecast uncertainty is present?

RQ3: Can probabilistic approaches improve robustness under renewable forecast uncertainty, and how do they affect operational security, redispatch needs, and market efficiency?

To answer these questions, the thesis introduces a simulation model of the four day-ahead subprocesses. The model incorporates configurable renewable forecast errors that may materialise at different stages (D-2, D-1 or D-0). By explicitly modelling the validation step alongside capacity calculation, market coupling, and redispatch, the framework provides a comprehensive picture of how forecast uncertainty propagates through the process chain. The results are evaluated against key performance indicators for efficiency, security, and robustness, thereby offering insights into how uncertainty-aware methods could enhance European capacity calculation and congestion management.

Methodology

To analyse the impact of renewable generation forecast errors on the capacity calculation and congestion management process chain, a dedicated simulation model was developed as part of this study. Existing modelling frameworks for flow-based market coupling are available [11, 22, 50, 44], but none fully address the requirements of the present research. Specifically, the model must capture all major process steps of the coordinated capacity calculation and congestion management chain as explained in section 2.1 — flow-based capacity calculation, validation, market coupling, and redispatch — while accommodating different realisations of renewable forecast errors. In addition, it should support both deterministic and probabilistic formulations, be openly accessible and well documented.

A central gap in the literature is the explicit modelling of the validation step, which is absent from existing tools but essential for representing the full process chain. In addition, most available frameworks are tailored to long-term multi-period studies and do not provide a consistent, scenario-based environment for analysing different uncertainty realisations of a single grid state. The model developed in this thesis, *munacco* — the Model for Uncertainty-aware Capacity Calculation and Congestion Management — addresses these limitations. The *munacco* module integrates renewable uncertainty through a scenario-based representation and a modular, process-oriented workflow. It mirrors the TSO process chain and, crucially, explicitly includes the validation stage.

The remainder of this chapter is structured as follows. Section 3.1 introduces the mathematical preliminaries, including optimisation concepts, notation, and the linearised power flow model. The treatment of renewable energy uncertainty and the scenario structure is presented in Section 3.2. Section 3.3 describes the market model, which covers the basecase, flow-based market coupling, and redispatch formulations. The validation model, a central contribution of this thesis, is presented in Section 3.4 for the deterministic case and the chance-constrained extension. Finally, Section 3.5 introduces the *munacco* software implementation, which integrates all subprocesses into a coherent workflow and provides the basis for the subsequent application and analysis.

3.1 Preliminaries on Power Flow Modeling

The core of the `munacco` framework is based on optimisation models combined with linear power flow representations. Optimisation provides a consistent mathematical language to describe decision-making under technical and economic constraints and is the standard approach in power system analysis and operations [52, 53]. All subprocesses of the capacity calculation workflow are expressed as optimisation problems.

In general, an optimisation problem can be written in the form

$$\begin{aligned} \min_x \quad & f(x) \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & g(x) \leq 0, \\ & h(x) = 0, \end{aligned} \tag{3.1}$$

where x denotes the decision variables, $f(x)$ the objective function, $g(x)$ the inequality constraints, and $h(x)$ the equality constraints. In the context of this thesis, the decision variables include generator dispatch, curtailment, and redispatch; objectives represent cost minimisation or parameter maximisation; and constraints ensure technical feasibility.

Within this framework, two model components can be distinguished. The first is the *market model*, covering the basecase, market coupling, and redispatch stages. Its formulations follow established approaches in the literature and build on existing optimisation models of flow-based market coupling [11, 22, 50, 44]. The second is the *validation model*, developed in this thesis as a novel contribution. Unlike the market formulations, validation has so far received little attention in the literature. This thesis introduces it explicitly, in both deterministic and probabilistic form, by applying chance constraints.

The following sections present the mathematical preliminaries, including notation and the linear power flow approximation, before describing the formulations of the market and validation models in detail.

3.1.1 Notation

The mathematical formulations in this thesis use a consistent notation for sets, indices, parameters, and variables. Sets are written in calligraphic font (e.g. \mathcal{G}), indices in lower case, decision variables in capital letters (e.g. G_g), and parameters in lower case with bars or superscripts if needed (e.g. \bar{p}_g). Vectors and matrices are denoted in boldface (e.g. \mathbf{INJ} , \mathbf{NP}). Subscripts denote indices, while superscripts carry descriptive information

such as time horizon t or type (e.g. forecasted \hat{p}_r^t). Random variables are written in Greek letters (e.g. ω_r^t).

Tab. 3.1.: Overview of notation used in the model.

Symbol	Description	Symbol	Description
Sets and indices		Parameters	
\mathcal{G}	Conventional generators	\bar{p}_g	Installed capacity of g
g	Index for conventional generators	\bar{p}_r	Installed capacity of r
\mathcal{R}	Renewable generators	c_g^{mc}	Marginal cost of g
\mathcal{R}^{unc}	Uncertain RES units	c_r^{mc}	Marginal cost of r
r	Index for renewable generators	c^{cu}	Curtailement penalty
\mathcal{N}	Nodes	c^{xb}	Cross-border redispatch cost
n	Index for nodes	c_g^{rd+}	Upward redispatch cost
\mathcal{Z}	Zones	c_g^{rd-}	Downward redispatch cost
z	Index for zones	\bar{f}_ℓ	Thermal line limit
\mathcal{L}	Transmission lines	ϕ_i	Voltage angle at i
ℓ	Index for lines	f_ℓ	Flow on line ℓ
\mathcal{V}	Set of Vertices	X_{ij}	Exchange from zone i to j
v	Vertex of the flow-based domain		
\mathcal{G}_n	Generators at node n		
\mathcal{R}_n	Renewables at node n		
\mathcal{N}_z	Nodes in zone z		
Decision variables		Vectors and Matrices	
G_g	Generation of g	INJ	Vector of nodal injections
CU_r	Curtailement of RES r	NP	Vector of zonal net positions
INJ_n	Nodal injection at node n	PTDF ^{nod}	Nodal PTDF matrix
NP_z	Zonal net position of z	PTDF ^{zon}	Zonal PTDF matrix
RD_g^+, RD_g^-	Up/down redispatch of g	\mathbf{A}	Node–branch incidence matrix
XB_z^+, XB_z^-	Up/down cross-border redispatch	\mathbf{B}_d	Diagonal susceptance matrix
IVA_ℓ	Individual Validation Adjustment	\mathbf{B}_ℓ	Line susceptance matrix
a	Vertex scaling factor	\mathbf{B}_n	Node susceptance matrix
		FRM	Flow Reliability Margins
		AMR	Adjustments for MinRAM
Forecast and uncertainty			
\hat{p}_r^t	Forecasted RES availability		
ω_r^t	Forecast error of r		
σ_r	Std. dev. of forecast error		
t	Forecast horizon index		

3.1.2 Linearised Power Flow

The modelling in this thesis relies on a linear approximation of power flows, commonly referred to as the DC load flow model. Most power systems worldwide operate with Alternating Current (AC), and the full AC power flow equations describe the relationships between active and reactive power injections, nodal voltages, and phase angles. However, solving these equations proves to be difficult because of the non-linear relation of the decision variables [45]. Formulations of the AC equations can be found in [54, 48]. In certain circumstances, a linearisation of the AC equations provides a sufficiently accurate approximation of the nonlinear solution [55].

The linearisation only calculates active power flows and relies on the following assumptions [45]:

- (i) line resistances are negligible compared to reactances
- (ii) voltage magnitudes are close to the nominal system voltage
- (iii) voltage angle differences across branches are small so that $\sin(\phi) \approx \phi$

Under these assumptions, the active power flow on a line $\ell = (i, j)$ with susceptance $b_{i,j}$ becomes

$$f_\ell = b_{i,j}(\phi_i - \phi_j) \quad (3.2)$$

where ϕ_i and ϕ_j are the voltage angles at the nodes i and j . The active power balance at a node i is given by

$$P_i = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} b_{i,j}(\phi_i - \phi_j). \quad (3.3)$$

These relations can be written compactly in matrix form. Here, \mathbf{A} denotes the node–branch incidence matrix of dimension $\mathcal{N} \times \mathcal{L}$, with entries $+1$ for the start node, -1 for the end node, and zero otherwise. \mathbf{B}_d describes the diagonal matrix of line susceptances, \mathbf{B}_ℓ and \mathbf{B}_n the line and node susceptance matrices. Then the branch flows and nodal injections can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{f} = \mathbf{B}_d \cdot \mathbf{A} \cdot \boldsymbol{\phi} = \mathbf{B}_\ell \cdot \boldsymbol{\phi}, \quad (3.4)$$

$$\mathbf{P}_n = \mathbf{A}^\top \cdot \mathbf{B}_d \cdot \mathbf{A} \cdot \boldsymbol{\phi} = \mathbf{B}_n \cdot \boldsymbol{\phi}. \quad (3.5)$$

The node-to-line sensitivity is then defined as the ratio between nodal power injections \mathbf{P}_n and the power flows \mathbf{f} :

$$\mathbf{PTDF}^{\text{nod}} = (\mathbf{B}_d \cdot \mathbf{A}) \cdot (\mathbf{A}^\top \cdot \mathbf{B}_d \cdot \mathbf{A})^{-1} \quad (3.6)$$

The nodal susceptance matrix $(\mathbf{A}^\top \mathbf{B}_d \mathbf{A})$ is singular and cannot be directly inverted. To resolve this, one node must be designated as a reference (or slack) node and excluded from the DC power flow equations. The voltage angle of this reference node is fixed to zero, which defines the angular reference for the entire system. The slack node also balances the system such that the sum of all nodal injections equals zero [56].

The derived PTDF provides the linear mapping between nodal power injections (\mathbf{P}_n) and active power flows on the transmission lines (\mathbf{f}) and is used in the following sections to introduce line capacity constraints and derive the zonal PTDF matrix for the flow-based computation.

3.2 Modelling of RES Uncertainty

Uncertainty in the model arises from renewable energy sources (RES). Following [57], curtailment interacts with forecast error by truncating the probability distribution of renewable output, complicating stochastic modelling. [58] propose a decision-dependent framework that optimizes curtailment ex-ante, while [59] show how output caps reshape wind output distributions in chance-constrained Optimal Power Flow (OPF).

In this thesis, each RES unit r is divided into two parts: a controllable share, which is dispatchable without forecast error, and an uncertain share, which is subject to forecast error and cannot be curtailed.

$$r = r^{ctrl} + r^{unc}, \quad \forall r \in \mathcal{R}. \quad (3.7)$$

The subset of uncertain units is then defined as $\mathcal{R}^{unc} \subset \mathcal{R}$. This clean separation allows the effects of forecast uncertainty and curtailment to be analysed independently, improving transparency and robustness of the analysis.

As a modelling assumption, the controllable share is parameterized by technology: 70% of wind capacity and 50% of PV capacity are assumed controllable. This choice reflects technology composition, with wind farms typically utility-scale and remotely controllable, while a large share of Photovoltaic (PV) remains rooftop-based and not dispatchable [60]. The remaining shares are modeled as uncertain and not subject to curtailment.

Each scenario comprises three forecast horizons $t \in \{D-2, D-1, D-0\}$, corresponding to capacity calculation, market coupling, and redispatch. In the absence of forecast error, renewable availability is

$$\hat{p}_r^t = p_r^{\max, pu} \cdot \bar{p}_r \quad \forall r \in \mathcal{R} \quad (3.8)$$

where \bar{p}_r is installed capacity and $p_r^{\max, pu}$ the per-unit scaling factor.

When forecast error applies, availability is perturbed as

$$\hat{p}_r^t = \left(p_r^{\max, pu} + \omega_r^t \right) \cdot \bar{p}_r, \quad \omega_r^t \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_r) \quad \forall r \in \mathcal{R}^{unc} \quad (3.9)$$

with values clipped to the physical range $[0, \bar{p}_r]$. Forecast errors are assumed normally distributed with zero mean [11, 61]. The standard deviation σ_r is defined relative to installed capacity, so that the absolute error is given by $\omega_r \cdot \bar{p}_r$. This ensures that larger units contribute proportionally more to absolute uncertainty while maintaining consistent relative variability across technologies.

3.3 Market Model

The market model in `munacco` consists of three optimisation problems representing the basecase in capacity calculation, the market coupling, and the redispatch stage. The formulations follow established approaches from the literature [11, 22, 50, 44]. The following assumptions apply throughout: the grid is modelled as a lossless linear power flow, generators bid at marginal costs without strategic behaviour, ramping of generators is not considered and demand is assumed to be fully inelastic.

All three stages are implemented as variants of a common Economic Dispatch Problem (EDP). The EDP establishes the basic optimisation framework, while each stage introduces additional constraints reflecting the specifics of capacity calculation, market coupling, or redispatch.

3.3.1 Base Economic Dispatch Problem

At the core of all three stages is a common Economic Dispatch Problem (EDP). The decision variables of the EDP are:

G_g	generation output of conventional generator $g \in \mathcal{G}$
CU_r	curtailment of renewable generator $r \in \mathcal{R}$
INJ_n	nodal injection at node $n \in \mathcal{N}$
NP_z	zonal net position of zone $z \in \mathcal{Z}$

The overall objective is the minimisation of total system costs, defined as the sum of generation costs, renewable generation costs, and renewable curtailment costs (Eq. 3.10a). Conventional generation costs are computed for each generator $g \in \mathcal{G}$ with its marginal generation costs c_g^{mc} , renewable generation is taken as the forecasted value \hat{p}_r^t reduced by curtailment multiplied by the renewable generation costs c_r^{mc} , and curtailment itself is penalised with the constant cost parameter c^{cu} . The forecast \hat{p}_r^t depends on the forecast horizon $t \in \{D-2, D-1, D-0\}$, corresponding to the values available for capacity calculation and validation ($D-2$), market coupling ($D-1$), and redispatch ($D-0$). Uncertainty in renewable generation can therefore be introduced by applying different forecast errors to these horizons as described in section 3.2.

The optimisation is subject to several sets of constraints. First, an energy balance is created for every node (Eq. 3.10b). The nodal injection INJ_n results from the total generation of conventional units at node n , plus renewable production reduced by curtailment, minus the nodal demand d_n . Zonal balances are then obtained by summing the injections of all nodes within zone z (Eq. 3.10c). Physical limits of conventional generators are enforced

by Eq. 3.10d, ensuring that output does not exceed installed capacity \bar{p}_g . Similarly, renewable curtailment is bounded by the forecasted available generation (Eq. 3.10e). For uncertain renewable units, curtailment is fixed to zero (Eq. 3.10f). Finally, system-wide power balance requires that the sum of all nodal injections equals zero (Eq. 3.10g).

$$\min \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} c_g^{\text{mc}} G_g + \sum_{r \in \mathcal{R}} c_r^{\text{mc}} (\hat{p}_r^t - CU_r) + c^{\text{cu}} \sum_{r \in \mathcal{R}} CU_r \quad (3.10a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}_n} G_g + \sum_{r \in \mathcal{R}_n} (\hat{p}_r^t - CU_r) - d_n = INJ_n \quad \forall n \in \mathcal{N} \quad (3.10b)$$

$$\sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}_z} INJ_n = NP_z \quad \forall z \in \mathcal{Z} \quad (3.10c)$$

$$0 \leq G_g \leq \bar{p}_g \quad \forall g \in \mathcal{G} \quad (3.10d)$$

$$0 \leq CU_r \leq \hat{p}_r^t \quad \forall r \in \mathcal{R} \quad (3.10e)$$

$$CU_r = 0 \quad \forall r \in \mathcal{R}^{\text{unc}} \quad (3.10f)$$

$$\sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} INJ_n = 0 \quad (3.10g)$$

Together, Eqs. 3.10a–3.10g define the basic EDP, which is then extended differently for the basecase and market coupling stages.

3.3.2 Basecase

The basecase is formulated as a nodal pricing problem [62], where generation costs are minimized while fully respecting the physical transmission constraints of the network. While this approach follows the basecase modeling of [11] and [22], it differs from operational practice where the basecase is derived from the forecasted CGM (see section 2.1.1). The nodal pricing formulation effectively assumes perfect information and full intra-zonal coordination, which removes internal congestions already at the basecase stage and can therefore underestimate the effect of minRAM.

The base EDP needs to be extended by explicitly including line flow limits for every critical network element. Flows are computed using the nodal PTDF matrix ($\mathbf{PTDF}^{\text{nod}}$) and the vector of nodal injections (INJ). The added line constraints in Eq. 3.11 ensure that resulting flows respect line capacity limits:

$$-\bar{f} \leq \mathbf{PTDF}^{\text{nod}} \cdot INJ \leq \bar{f} \quad (3.11)$$

Here, $\mathbf{PTDF}^{\text{nod}}$ denotes the matrix of node-to-line sensitivities, and \bar{f} is the vector of maximum permissible flows. Since the basecase is computed two days before delivery,

it uses the forecast horizon $t = D - 2$ in equations 3.10a, 3.10b and 3.10e. From the basecase solution, the flow-based parameters are derived.

3.3.3 Flow-Based Parameters

As described in Section 2.1.1, the flow-based parameters consist of zonal Power Transfer Distribution Factors ($\mathbf{PTDF}^{\text{zon}}$) and the Remaining Available Margin (RAM) for each CNEC.

The translation from node-to-line to zone-to-line sensitivities requires Generation Shift Keys (GSK), which distribute changes in zonal net positions to the individual generators. Two options are implemented in the model: a flat GSK strategy, assigning equal shares to all conventional generators in the zone (*flat*), and a capacity-weighted GSK strategy, where shares are proportional to the maximum generation capacity \bar{p}_g (*gmax*) [39].

The zonal PTDF is obtained as described in [20]:

$$\mathbf{PTDF}^{\text{zon}} = \mathbf{PTDF}^{\text{nod}} \cdot \mathbf{GSK}, \quad (3.12)$$

Following that, the equation to determine RAM is also provided by [20]:

$$\mathbf{RAM} = \bar{\mathbf{f}} - \mathbf{f}_0 - \mathbf{FRM} + \mathbf{AMR}, \quad (3.13)$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{f}}$ is the thermal line capacity, \mathbf{f}_0 is the basecase line loading corrected for cross-zonal exchanges, FRM denotes the Flow Reliability Margin, and AMR represents the Adjustment for MinRAM application.

The basecase flow without zonal exchanges \mathbf{f}_0 is calculated by subtracting the line loading resulting from non-zero net positions from the line loading obtained in the basecase.

$$\mathbf{f}_0 = \mathbf{PTDF}^{\text{nod}} \cdot \mathbf{INJ}^{BC} - \mathbf{PTDF}^{\text{zon}} \cdot \mathbf{NP}^{BC} \quad (3.14)$$

with \mathbf{INJ}^{BC} denoting nodal injections and \mathbf{NP}^{BC} zonal net positions in the basecase.

The AMR ensures that the minimum RAM requirement is fulfilled by adjusting available capacity upwards if the calculated RAM falls below the enforced threshold:

$$\mathbf{AMR} = \max \left(0, \min\text{RAM} \cdot \bar{\mathbf{f}} - \left(\bar{\mathbf{f}} - \mathbf{f}_0 - \mathbf{FRM} \right) \right). \quad (3.15)$$

3.3.4 Market Coupling

The market coupling stage extends the base EDP by introducing flow-based capacity constraints that restrict the feasible set of zonal net positions. Resulting flows in the market coupling optimisation problem are computed as the product of the vector of zonal net positions (NP) and the zonal PTDF ($PTDF^{z\text{on}}$). These flows must remain within the allowed RAM [11]:

$$PTDF^{z\text{on}} \cdot NP \leq RAM \quad (3.16)$$

The market coupling problem is solved using Eqs. 3.10a–3.10g and the added constraint (3.16) for the forecast horizon $t = D - 1$, reflecting that updated renewable forecasts are available at the day-ahead stage.

3.3.5 Redispatch

The redispatch stage is designed to resolve any residual network congestion that persists subsequent to market coupling by adjusting generator outputs and renewable curtailment. Rather than recalculating the entire economic dispatch, the redispatch model is formulated to optimize corrective actions on top of the pre-established market outcome, using a so-called *cost-based* redispatch model [22]. Specifically, it extends the base EDP by incorporating additional decision variables that represent redispatch measures.

The solution of the flow-based market coupling optimisation at $t = D - 1$ provides generator outputs G_g^{MC} and zonal net positions NP_z^{MC} . The redispatch stage introduces the following additional decision variables for corrective actions at $t = D - 0$:

$$\begin{aligned} RD_g^+, RD_g^- & \text{ upward and downward redispatch of conventional generator } g \in \mathcal{G} \\ XB_z^+, XB_z^- & \text{ upward and downward cross-border redispatch of the net position of} \\ & \text{zone } z \in \mathcal{Z} \end{aligned}$$

Cross-border redispatch serves as a representation of coordination between bidding zones in the redispatch stage, allowing zonal net positions to deviate by up to a specified limit \overline{XB} from the previously established market-coupling values. If $\overline{XB} = 0$, the corrective measures are strictly constrained to be intra-zonal, permitting no deviation in zonal net positions.

The post-redispach generator outputs and zonal net positions are defined as:

$$G_g^{\text{RD}} = G_g^{\text{MC}} + RD_g^+ - RD_g^-, \quad \forall g \in \mathcal{G} \quad (3.17)$$

$$NP_z^{\text{RD}} = NP_z^{\text{MC}} + XB_z^+ - XB_z^-, \quad \forall z \in \mathcal{Z} \quad (3.18)$$

The resulting optimisation problem is described in the following.

$$\begin{aligned} \min \quad & \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} \left(c_g^{\text{rd}+} RD_g^+ + c_g^{\text{rd}-} RD_g^- \right) \\ & + c^{\text{cu}} \sum_{r \in \mathcal{R}} CU_r \\ & + c^{\text{xb}} \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} \left(XB_z^+ + XB_z^- \right) \end{aligned} \quad (3.19a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{s.t.} \quad & \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}_n} \left(G_g^{\text{MC}} + RD_g^+ - RD_g^- \right) \\ & + \sum_{r \in \mathcal{R}_n} \left(\hat{p}_r^{\text{D}-0} - CU_r \right) - d_n = INJ_n \quad \forall n \in \mathcal{N} \end{aligned} \quad (3.19b)$$

$$\sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}_z} INJ_n = NP_z^{\text{MC}} + XB_z^+ - XB_z^- \quad \forall z \in \mathcal{Z} \quad (3.19c)$$

$$0 \leq G_g^{\text{MC}} + RD_g^+ - RD_g^- \leq \bar{p}_g \quad \forall g \in \mathcal{G} \quad (3.19d)$$

$$0 \leq CU_r \leq \hat{p}_r^{\text{D}-0} \quad \forall r \in \mathcal{R} \quad (3.19e)$$

$$CU_r = 0 \quad \forall r \in \mathcal{R}_{\text{unc}} \quad (3.19f)$$

$$\sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} INJ_n = 0 \quad (3.19g)$$

$$-\bar{f} \leq \mathbf{PTDF}^{\text{nod}} \cdot \mathbf{INJ} \leq \bar{f} \quad (3.19h)$$

$$0 \leq XB_z^+ \leq \overline{XB}, \quad 0 \leq XB_z^- \leq \overline{XB} \quad \forall z \in \mathcal{Z} \quad (3.19i)$$

The objective function (3.19a) minimizes the total cost of corrective measures. All redispatch measures are penalized with positive costs, ensuring that the optimisation seeks only to resolve congestions and does not re-optimize the system. The first cost term accounts for upward and downward redispatch of conventional generators. In the model, penalties for positive redispatch ($c^{\text{rd}+}$) are based on the variable production costs of the respective unit, ensuring that units with lower operating costs are preferred for upward redispatch. Penalties for negative redispatch ($c^{\text{rd}-}$) are derived by subtracting the unit's variable costs from the maximum variable costs across all units. As a result, units with the highest variable costs are prioritized for downward redispatch. To both penalty terms, a fixed base value of 30 EUR/MWh is [22]. Curtailment is modelled as the most expensive and therefore least attractive measure to relieve congestion. Here, the

maximum variable cost of all generators with an addition of 100 EUR/MWh is applied as penalty (c^{cu}). When reporting redispatch costs in Chapter 4, they consist of the difference in marginal costs that have to be paid between negative and positive redispatch, the base redispatch cost for every unit redispatched and curtailment costs that are priced with 100 EUR/MWh.

Cross-border redispatch, which shifts zonal net positions away from the market coupling outcome, is associated with penalty c^{xb} and constrained by an upper bound \overline{XB} (Eq. 3.19i). By setting high costs for cross-border corrections c^{xb} the optimisation is incentivized to prioritize intra-zonal redispatch before cross-zonal redispatch.

The nodal balance constraint (3.19b) ensures the energy balance at every node, considering redispatch activities, RES availability at day of delivery (\hat{p}_r^{D-0}) reduced by curtailment and the nodal demand. Similarly, the zonal balance (3.19c) links nodal injections to the updated zonal net positions. Generator output bounds (3.19d) guarantee that redispatch measures do not exceed physical generation limits, while curtailment bounds (3.19e) prevent RES curtailment beyond forecasted feed-in. As before, non-curtable (uncertain) RES are fixed to zero curtailment in (3.19f). The global system balance is imposed in (3.19g), ensuring that total injections across all nodes sum to zero. Power flow feasibility is enforced by (3.19h) using nodal dispatch and incorporating all line constraints, as in the basecase formulation. The last constraint (3.19i) limits the amount of cross-border redispatch by setting the maximum allowed deviation of the zones net position from the market result \overline{XB} .

3.3.6 Computation of Zonal Exchanges

In order to translate a given vector of zonal net positions into bilateral exchanges between zones, a secondary optimisation problem is solved. The objective is to find the minimal set of exchanges that exactly reproduce the zonal net positions while avoiding unnecessary trade volume. This is achieved by requiring that the sum of all bilateral exports of a zone equals its net position, and that exchanges are symmetric ($X_{ij} = -X_{ji}$). The optimisation then minimises the overall exchange volume, yielding the solution with the smallest set of consistent trades.

NP_i denotes the zonal net position and X_{ij} the exchange from zone i to j . The problem is given by

$$\min_{\mathbf{X}} \sum_i \sum_j X_{ij} \quad (3.20a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \sum_j X_{ij} = NP_i \quad \forall i, \quad (3.20b)$$

$$X_{ij} = -X_{ji}, \quad X_{ii} = 0. \quad (3.20c)$$

This approach ensures that the resulting exchange matrix \mathbf{X} is consistent with the net positions and contains the minimum amount of bilateral trading necessary. It is used throughout the model to visualise and report zonal exchanges.

3.4 Validation Model

As outlined in Section 2.1.2, validation constitutes a pivotal step within the CACM process chain. The flow-based domain obtained from the capacity calculation stage, which has been enlarged through the application of minRAM, requires validation to ensure operational security of probable market outcomes. Despite its central role in practice, no explicit implementation of validation could be identified in the scientific literature to date. The approach presented here is therefore based on the methodology of the DAVinCy (Day-Ahead Validation of Capacity) procedure, which has been jointly developed by the four German TSOs together with APG (Austria) and TTN (Netherlands). While publicly available documentation is scarce, the general principles are described in [35]. The terminology used in this study follows the one used for the Individual Validation.

The main concept of the validation process is explained in section 2.1.2. Two main principles for the validation could be concluded:

1. A selection of possible market outcomes is to be validated. A validated point must be plausible with respect to the forecasted net positions, technically feasible and close to the edge of the flow-based domain.
2. IVAs can only be applied if all available RAs are not sufficient to solve congestions resulting from the validated position

The following subsections describe the implementation of these two principles in detail.

Fig. 3.1.: Selection of vertices for the validation process based on angle to NPF

3.4.1 Vertex Selection

The starting point of validation is the set of vertices (= corners) of the flow-based domain obtained from the capacity calculation stage. A selection criterion is applied to identify only those vertices that represent probable market directions. The guiding assumption is that the NPF obtained from the basecase result provides a reasonable estimate of the likely market outcome. Vertices close to this forecast in directional terms are therefore selected for validation.

Formally, $\mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{Z}|}$ denotes the zonal net positions corresponding to a candidate vertex, and $\mathbf{NPF} \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{Z}|}$ represents the vector of forecasted net positions from the basecase. The angle between these two vectors is defined as

$$\theta(\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{NPF}) = \arccos \left(\frac{\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{NPF}}{\|\mathbf{v}\| \|\mathbf{NPF}\|} \right). \quad (3.21)$$

A vertex \mathbf{v} is selected for validation if

$$\theta(\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{NPF}) \leq \theta^{\max}, \quad (3.22)$$

where θ^{\max} is a predefined maximum angle threshold. Fig. 3.1 shows a schematic example of the vertex selection.

As mentioned above, this approach relies on the assumption that the NPF provides a good estimate of the actual market clearing result. Although this assumption may not always hold, it reflects practical procedures, as most TSO implementations also rely on forecasted NPF for the vertex selection step [35].

3.4.2 Deterministic Validation

The second validation principle as well as the condition to only validate technically feasible net positions is implemented through a two-stage optimisation process. The central idea is to first assess whether a selected vertex can be physically realised under generator and load constraints and in a second step assess the feasibility including line constraints. Only if a vertex is feasible in the first stage but infeasible in the second stage, IVAs are applied.

As the grid topology is assumed to be fixed in the model, *all available remedial actions* (see section 2.1.2) reduce to the use of redispatch. A key difficulty is that at the validation stage the actual market outcome and the corresponding generator dispatch and grid situation are not yet known. Additionally, one combination of zonal net positions can correspond to infinitely many internal grid states, each with different generator outputs, renewable dispatch levels, and resulting line flows. The modeling approach adopted here assumes that if there exists at least one feasible grid situation without remaining congestions for a given zonal net position combination, this outcome can be reached through redispatch from any other grid situation with the same zonal net positions. Thus, the validation problem reduces to checking whether an economic dispatch problem can find a feasible solution for a given set of zonal net positions. As explained in section 3.3.5, *munacco* includes the optional use of cross-border redispatch. Cross-border redispatch is not considered in the implementation of the validation.

Each vertex is represented by its zonal net position vector $v \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{Z}|}$, where v_z denotes the net position of zone $z \in \mathcal{Z}$. For the optimisation, a new decision variable $a \geq 0$ is introduced, representing a scalar scaling factor of the selected vertex. The objective of the problem is to maximise a (Eq. (3.23a)). This can be interpreted as moving along the straight line from the origin of the flow-based domain to the selected vertex, thereby identifying the furthest feasible point in the direction of the vertex (Fig. 3.2). In the first stage, the scalar factor a^{\max} is determined, by solving without line constraints, indicating the ability of the market to reach a certain net position. Higher factors would result in unrealistic net positions that can not be reached by the system. In the second stage the scaling factor a^* including line constraints is obtained, determining operationally secure and insecure net positions in the direction of the chosen vertex. As shown in Fig. 3.2, three regions can be distinguished. An operationally secure (green) region until $a^* \cdot v$ is reached, an operationally insecure (red) region between $a^* \cdot v$ and $a^{\max} \cdot v$ and a not reachable (yellow) region of technically infeasible net positions. The operationally insecure region only exists if $a^* < a^{\max}$ and $a^* < 1$.

The optimisation problem to obtain a^{\max} and a^* closely mirrors the constraints of the base economic dispatch problem (EDP), ensuring nodal (3.23b) and zonal (3.23c) energy

Fig. 3.2.: Depiction of two stage validation procedure.

balance, enforcing generator capacity limits (3.23d), restricting renewable curtailment according to forecasted availability (3.23e) and curtailment possibility (3.23f) and ensuring system balance (3.23g). The line constraints (3.23h) are formulated as in the base EDP but only used in the second stage optimisation. In particular, in the zonal energy balance the net position NP_z is replaced by the scaled vertex position $a \cdot v_z$ (3.23c), thereby directly linking the optimisation outcome to the directional feasibility of the chosen vertex. It is important to note, that this implementation takes the forecasted renewable availability \hat{p}_r^{D-2} as input for evaluation. It therefore represents the deterministic version without considering uncertainty in the forecast. A second, uncertainty-aware, validation methodology is described in 3.4.4.

$$\forall v \in \mathcal{V}^{sel} :$$

$$\max \quad a \quad (3.23a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}_n} G_g + \sum_{r \in \mathcal{R}_n} (\hat{p}_r^{D-2} - CU_r) - d_n = INJ_n \quad \forall n \in \mathcal{N} \quad (3.23b)$$

$$\sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}_z} INJ_n = a \cdot v_z \quad \forall z \in \mathcal{Z} \quad (3.23c)$$

$$0 \leq G_g \leq \bar{p}_g \quad \forall g \in \mathcal{G} \quad (3.23d)$$

$$0 \leq CU_r \leq \hat{p}_r^{D-2} \quad \forall r \in \mathcal{R} \quad (3.23e)$$

$$CU_r = 0 \quad \forall r \in \mathcal{R}_{\text{uncertain}} \quad (3.23f)$$

$$\sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} INJ_n = 0 \quad \forall n \in \mathcal{N} \quad (3.23g)$$

$$-\bar{f} \leq \mathbf{PTDF}^{\text{nod}} \cdot \mathbf{INJ} \leq \bar{f} \quad (3.23h)$$

For each selected vertex, the validation optimisation is solved twice. In the first stage, the problem is formulated by equations (3.23a)–(3.23g) without line constraints. The

Fig. 3.3.: Domain restriction due to IVA application on multiple CNECs.

resulting solution is defined as a^{\max} . In the second stage, the line flow constraints (3.23h) are added and the optimisation problem yields the scaling factor a^* . Since the second problem only introduces additional constraints, it follows directly that $a^* \leq a^{\max}$. The computation of IVAs from the scaling factor values is explained in the following section.

3.4.3 IVA Computation

To exclude operationally insecure regions of the flow-based domain, vertices for which $a^* < a^{\max}$ and $a^* < 1$ must be proportionally shifted inwards. Formally, the validated vertex position is given by

$$\mathbf{v}^{\text{validated}} = a^* \cdot \mathbf{v}, \quad (3.24)$$

where \mathbf{v} denotes the original zonal net position vector of the vertex. The reduction factor a^* is therefore directly translated into proportional adjustments of the RAM of the limiting network elements. In practice, this adjustment is implemented through IVAs applied to the CNECs that form the respective vertex, from here on referred to as *incident CNECs*¹. In Fig. 3.3, CNEC 1 and CNEC 2 are incident to vertex V1. Therefore IVAs have to be applied to both CNECs to move the vertex inwards to $a^* \cdot \mathbf{v}_1$.

For each selected vertex \mathbf{v} , the set of incident CNECs $L_v \subseteq L$ is identified by the condition

$$\sum \text{PTDF}_\ell^{\text{zon}} \cdot \mathbf{v} = \text{RAM}_\ell, \quad \forall \ell \in L_v, \quad (3.25)$$

i.e., those CNECs that are exactly saturated by the vertex position. For every $\ell \in L_v$, the IVA is then computed as

$$\text{IVA}_\ell = \begin{cases} (1 - a^*) \cdot \text{RAM}_\ell, & \text{if } a^* < a^{\max} \text{ and } a^* < 1, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (3.26)$$

¹The terminology is taken from graph theory, where an edge is defined as incident to a node or vertex, if it connects to it [63].

This value represents the proportional reduction of available margin required to shift the vertex inwards to its validated position. Since a single CNEC can be incident to multiple vertices, multiple IVA values may be computed for the same element. In the illustrated example CNEC 2 is incident to two validated vertices, resulting in two IVAs. To ensure conservativeness, the effective IVA for each CNEC ℓ is chosen as the maximum value across all vertices:

$$\text{IVA}_\ell^{\text{final}} = \max_{v \in V_{\text{sel}}} \text{IVA}_\ell(v) \quad \forall \ell \in \mathcal{L} \quad (3.27)$$

The corrected margin of CNEC ℓ after IVA application is then given by

$$\text{RAM}_\ell^{\text{new}} = \text{RAM}_\ell - \text{IVA}_\ell^{\text{final}} \quad \forall \ell \in \mathcal{L} \quad (3.28)$$

This procedure ensures that all potentially insecure vertices are shifted inwards consistently, while the most restrictive adjustment is applied to each network element across the domain. The obtained domain is called validated domain. The resulting RAM values are used in the flow-based market coupling process, described in 3.3.4.

3.4.4 Probabilistic Validation via Chance Constraints

The validation formulation presented so far represents a deterministic process, assuming perfect foresight of renewable generation at $t = D-0$ through the forecasted availability $\hat{p}_r^{\text{D}-2}$ in Eq. (3.23b). In practice, however, forecast errors in renewable energy production create deviations that challenge this assumption. To explicitly account for such uncertainty, the deterministic validation is extended into a probabilistic framework by means of chance constraints.

Chance constraints provide a structured way to implement robustness against uncertainty within optimisation problems: they ensure that technical limits are satisfied with a predefined probability rather than with certainty. This approach has been widely applied in academic research on power flow optimisation under uncertainty [59, 64, 49, 47], and can be integrated into existing formulations with limited modifications. In this thesis, the chance-constrained validation follows the equations proposed in [11].

As introduced in Eq. (3.9), the forecasted availability can be represented as $\hat{p}_r(\omega_r) = f(\omega_r)$, where ω_r denotes a zero-mean random forecast error of renewable generator $r \in \mathcal{R}_{\text{uncertain}}$. The aggregated deviation $\omega \cdot \bar{p}$ introduces a system imbalance which must be absorbed by conventional generators. To model this corrective adjustment, a participation factor $0 \leq \alpha_g \leq 1$ is defined for each generator $g \in \mathcal{G}$, allocating a share of the total RES forecast error to the generator. The adjusted generator dispatch therefore becomes

$$G_g(\omega) = G_g - \alpha_g(\omega \cdot \bar{p}) \quad (3.29)$$

The participation factor can either be defined beforehand, similar to GSKs, or left as a decision variable in the optimisation problem.

For a more detailed discussion of participation factors and their role in uncertainty-aware capacity calculation, see [11, 48, 47]. The resulting optimisation problem is formulated as follows:

$$\max \quad a \quad (3.30a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}_n} G_g(\boldsymbol{\omega}) + \sum_{r \in \mathcal{R}_n} (\hat{p}_r(\omega_r) - CU_r) - d_n = INJ_n \quad \forall n \in \mathcal{N} \quad (3.30b)$$

$$\sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}_z} INJ_n = a v_z \quad \forall z \in \mathcal{Z} \quad (3.30c)$$

$$0 \leq CU_r \leq \hat{p}_r(\omega_r) \quad \forall r \in \mathcal{R} \quad (3.30d)$$

$$CU_r = 0 \quad \forall r \in \mathcal{R}_{\text{uncertain}} \quad (3.30e)$$

$$\sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} INJ_n = 0 \quad (3.30f)$$

$$\mathbb{P}\left\{ 0 \leq G_g(\boldsymbol{\omega}) \leq \bar{p}_g \right\} \geq 1 - \varepsilon \quad \forall g \in \mathcal{G} \quad (3.30g)$$

$$\mathbb{P}\left\{ -\bar{f}_\ell \leq \mathbf{PTDF}_\ell^{\text{nod}} \cdot INJ \leq \bar{f}_\ell \right\} \geq 1 - \varepsilon \quad \forall \ell \in \mathcal{L} \quad (3.30h)$$

Constraints (3.30g) and (3.30h) are so-called chance constraints, which ensure that generator capacities and line flows are respected with a probability of at least $(1 - \varepsilon)$. The parameter ε defines the tolerated risk level and is typically chosen to be small (e.g., $\varepsilon = 5\%$) [49, 48]. Since these constraints are probabilistic, they introduce robustness into the validation problem by explicitly accounting for forecast uncertainty.

However, directly solving chance constraints in their raw form is generally impossible due to their non-convex nature. To enable computationally efficient solutions, they are commonly reformulated into deterministic equivalents [47, 49]. When renewable forecast errors are modeled as Gaussian or, more broadly, as elliptical distributions and the constraints are affine, these reformulations can be expressed as second-order conic constraints [47]. This transformation makes the overall chance-constrained problem manageable and allows it to be solved with Second Order Cone Programming Solvers [11]. A detailed description of this reformulation process can be found in [47, 11].

In contrast to the deterministic validation, the chance-constrained formulation integrates uncertainty directly into the validation process. As a consequence, market outcomes that would appear feasible under perfect foresight but are likely to violate operational limits under realistic forecast errors are systematically excluded from the validated flow-based domain. The chance-constrained formulation can be seen as an extension of the

deterministic validation, maintaining the same overall structure but embedding stochastic robustness.

3.5 The munacco Module

The munacco framework provides an implementation of the capacity calculation and congestion management chain, that is specifically designed to incorporate renewable uncertainty at different stages. Its workflow, shown in Figure 3.4, takes a network description and uncertainty settings as input, generates scenarios of renewable availability, and processes them through the four subprocesses: capacity calculation, validation, market coupling, and redispatch. Outputs are stored per scenario and can be inspected individually or aggregated for performance analysis.

Fig. 3.4.: Workflow of the munacco module. Inputs (green), data processing modules (grey), core CACM module (blue), and data classes (orange).

Inputs

The structural input is the grid topology, represented by the `NetworkData` class. Nodes host generators, loads, and RES units, are grouped into zones, and are interconnected by transmission lines. Attributes include generator capacities and costs, renewable availability, demand, and line parameters. Data can be imported either from PyPSA `.nc`

files or from a set of CSV tables (nodes, lines, generators, RES). Uncertainty parameters define which RES are controllable and which are uncertain, and specify forecast error standard deviations.

Scenario Generation

The `ScenarioGenerator` creates scenarios by perturbing the availability of uncertain RES with normally distributed forecast errors, while controllable RES retain their forecast values. Each scenario stores renewable availability at three forecast horizons (D-2, D-1, D-0) corresponding to the subprocesses. The `Scenario` class bundles these values with a reference to the common `NetworkData`.

Core CACM Module

The central controller is the `CACMModel`, which sequentially executes the subprocesses for each scenario. It is configured via a `.json`² options file, allowing the user to select basecase formulations, generator shift key strategies, validation mode (deterministic or chance-constrained), and redispatch settings.

The `MarketModel` handles the three market-related steps (basecase, market coupling, redispatch). The `Validator` performs vertex selection and validation, and applies Individual Validation Adjustments (IVA). Results of all subprocesses are stored in the `Results` class associated with each scenario.

Analysis

Two analysis modules are provided. The `ScenarioInspector` enables detailed inspection of individual scenarios, including domain plots and dispatch visualisation. The `Analyzer` aggregates results across scenarios, computes key performance indicators, and allows comparison between model configurations.

Example Application

Listing 3.1 shows a minimal example of the complete workflow. The network is loaded, RES are split into controllable and uncertain shares, whereby the controllable part is defined. 100 scenarios are generated, the CACM chain is executed, and results are analysed and visualised for the first scenario.

```
1 import munacco as mc
2
3 # Step 1: Load network and split RES
4 network = mc.InputLoader().load_from_csv("data/base_model/")
5 network.split_res_generators({'wind': 0.7, 'solar': 0.5})
6 network.initialize()
7
8 # Step 2: Generate scenarios
9 scenarios = mc.ScenarioGenerator().generate(
```

²<https://www.json.org/json-en.html>

```

10     network, n_scenarios=100, forecast_timing=['d1', 'd0'])
11
12 # Step 3: Run CACM model
13 model = mc.CACMModel(options_path="options_default.json")
14 model.batchrun(scenarios)
15
16 # Step 4: Aggregate results
17 analyzer = mc.Analyzer(scenarios)
18 print("Scenarios with overloads:",
19       sum(analyzer.df.remaining_overload))
20
21 # Step 5: Inspect one scenario
22 inspector = mc.ScenarioInspector(scenarios[0])
23 inspector.create_domain_plot(('Z1', 'Z2'), ('Z2', 'Z3'),
24                             result='market_coupling')

```

Listing 3.1: Example usage of the munacco module

3.5.1 Code and Data Availability

The full implementation of the modelling framework developed in this thesis is openly available on GitHub at <https://github.com/mvoitl/munacco>. The corresponding input data, including input networks and result data of the following applications, is archived on Zenodo under <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17226797> [65], ensuring permanent accessibility and reproducibility.

All simulations were executed in Python 3.11.9 on a machine running Windows Server 2019 Standard, equipped with four Intel® Xeon® Gold 6348 CPUs (2.60 GHz) and 128 GB RAM.

Application

This chapter applies the `munacco` framework to analyse the impact of renewable forecast uncertainty on the processes of capacity calculation, validation, market coupling, and redispatch. The analyses are structured to address the research questions formulated in Section 2.4.

In order to study the methodology in a transparent and reproducible setting, a minimalistic 4-node network is introduced. The objective of this case study is to create a controlled environment in which the effects of the different subprocesses in the `munacco` framework can be isolated and illustrated in detail. Although the network is highly stylised compared to a realistic transmission grid, a 4-node/3-zone network is sufficiently complex to capture the structure of flow-based market coupling processes [66]. The use of a small system provides several benefits:

- A limited number of network elements makes it easier to understand the interactions between capacity calculation, validation, market coupling, and redispatch.
- Results are easier to interpret, as fewer parameters influence the outcomes.
- The system provides a benchmark for testing whether the model reacts as intended.

The small example in section 4.1 is used to assess the main research objectives before turning to a large-scale application in section 4.3, in order to test whether the insights obtained in the stylised case hold in a larger system.

4.1 Case Study on a 4-Node Network

The main analysis of this study are conducted on a simplified 3-zone/4-node network, which is shown in Figure 4.1. The network consists of 3 zones (Z1-Z3) and 4 nodes (N1-N4). Nodes 2 and 3 belong to Zone 2, while Nodes 1 and 4 each represent individual zones. Each node is connected one conventional generator, a demand, and nodes N2-N4 additionally host a renewable energy source. The nodes are connected by 5 transmission lines. Line susceptance values are chosen to be equal ($b = 1$) for all lines. Line capacities

are set to be 100 MW for lines L1, L3, L4 and L5, while L2 has a maximum capacity of 30 MW.

Fig. 4.1.: Topology of 4-node / 3-zone network with line capacities.

The attributes of nodes, generators and RES are listed in tables 4.1, 4.2 and 4.3 respectively. Demands vary from 50 MW at Node 2 to 150 MW at Nodes 1 and 4. As explained in 3.1.2 a slack node needs to be defined, which, in this case, is Node 3.

Tab. 4.1.: Nodes and zones 4-node system

Nodes \mathcal{N}	Zones \mathcal{Z}	Demand d [MW]	Slack
N1	Z1	150	No
N2	Z2	50	No
N3	Z2	100	Yes
N4	Z3	150	No

Generators (see table 4.2) have different marginal costs and maximum production capacities. For the implementation of probabilistic validation (see section 3.4.4), Generators 2 and 3 are assumed to adjust their dispatch to forecast errors and are therefore assigned a participation factor α^1 .

Tab. 4.2.: Conventional generators in the 4-node system.

Generators \mathcal{G}	Cost mc [€/MWh]	Capacity \bar{p} [MW]	α	Location
G1	80	150	False	N1
G2	50	100	True	N2
G3	40	70	True	N3
G4	70	250	False	N4

Additionally, two forms of RES are integrated into the system. A large wind farm at Node 2 and two smaller PV plants at Nodes 3 and 4. The forecasted availabilities ($p^{\max,pu}$)

¹The value of α is determined as part of the chance-constrained optimisation problem.

are set to 80% for the wind farm and 70% for the PV plants, corresponding to an hour with high renewable availability. All RES have very low marginal costs compared to the conventional generators. This matches the economic logic behind the merit order effect, where renewables, due to their low marginal costs, are dispatched before conventional units, pushing higher-cost generators out of the market during periods of high renewable output [67].

Tab. 4.3.: Renewable energy sources in the 4-node system.

RES \mathcal{R}	Cost mc [€/MWh]	Capacity \bar{p} [MW]	Forecast $p^{\max,pu}$	Location
Wind 2	0.12	300	0.8	N2
PV 3	0.11	50	0.7	N3
PV 4	0.10	100	0.7	N4

Overall, Zone 2 can be characterized as a net export zone, as it combines high renewable infeed with low-cost conventional generation. In particular, Node 2, hosting the large wind farm, has high renewable export potential. By contrast, Zone 1 is designed to be an import-oriented zone, since it exhibits high demand and only has access to the most expensive conventional generator. Finally, the network topology is deliberately chosen such that congestion is likely to occur on the internal line L2 of Zone 2, representing a structural bottleneck between the two nodes of the zone.

This network serves as the base for the following analysis. First, the impact of forecast uncertainty on the sub-processes capacity calculation and validation is assessed. Then, a single scenario is analysed more extensively introducing a chance-constrained version of the validation. Following that, the effectiveness of the implementation is assessed in a case study with multiple scenarios and a sensitivity analysis of the risk tolerance parameter in the probabilistic implementation is conducted.

4.1.1 Impact of Uncertainty on Capacity Calculation and Validation

This section addresses the first research sub-question to determine, which subprocesses of capacity calculation and congestion management are most affected by renewable forecast uncertainty, and thus most relevant for integrating uncertainty into decision making.

As outlined in Section 2.2, the TSO-controlled subprocesses most relevant for integrating forecast uncertainty are capacity calculation and validation. Market coupling itself is a market operation and cannot explicitly account for forecast uncertainty, while redispatch occurs in real time and is therefore based on realised renewable availability. Capacity calculation and validation, in contrast, are conducted at D-2, when forecast uncertainty is largest, and their outcomes strongly influence both the flow-based domain available

to the market and the redispatch requirements at a later stage. The role of minRAM is particularly important, as it constitutes the final adjustment of the flow-based parameters in the capacity calculation before validation. By enlarging the flow-based domain, it simultaneously increases the necessity of validation to ensure operational security (see Sections 2.1.1 and 2.1.2).

To study the role of forecast uncertainty in these subprocesses, a reference scenario without any forecast error is compared to 300 alternative scenarios (\mathcal{S}). In the reference case, the forecasts at D-2, D-1, and D-0 are identical. In the alternative scenarios, the D-2 forecasts are varied to reflect forecast errors, while D-1 and D-0 remain fixed. This setup mimics the situation in which TSOs take their capacity calculation and validation decisions at D-2 under uncertain conditions, and allows analysing how different forecast inputs translate into different flow-based domains and, ultimately, different market results.

The effect of these forecast scenarios is measured by comparing the resulting MCPs to the reference case. The deviation of the net position combination of the market result in a scenario ($\mathbf{NP}_s^{\text{MC}}$) from the reference market result ($\mathbf{NP}_{ref}^{\text{MC}}$) is quantified using the the Euclidean distance between them:

$$d_s = \|\mathbf{NP}_{ref}^{\text{MC}} - \mathbf{NP}_s^{\text{MC}}\|_2, \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S}. \quad (4.1)$$

Small deviations indicate that the process is largely insensitive to forecast uncertainty, whereas large deviations signal that the process strongly depends on the D-2 forecasts.

In the munacco model, a set of 300 scenarios is generated, each representing a different D-2 forecast realisation. The standard deviation of all renewable sources is set to $\sigma = 20\%$ of installed capacity, while D-1 and D-0 forecast values remain fixed at the product of installed capacity \bar{p} and availability $p^{\text{max},pu}$ according to Table 4.3. A scenario without forecast error ($\hat{p}^{D-2} = \hat{p}^{D-1} = \hat{p}^{D-0}$) serves as the reference case. To analyse the interaction with minRAM, model runs are performed for values between 0% and 50%. In order to separate the effect on capacity calculation from the effect on validation, each run is conducted both with and without the inclusion of the validation step:

1. Capacity Calculation \rightarrow Market Coupling
2. Capacity Calculation \rightarrow Validation \rightarrow Market Coupling

Figures 4.2 and 4.3 present the results of this analysis. Figure 4.2 shows the distribution of MCP deviations, measured as the Euclidean distance from the reference case, across 300 renewable forecast scenarios for different values of the minRAM. The flow-based domains corresponding to the 0% and 40% minRAM cases are shown in Fig. 4.3. For each of these settings, the domains and resulting MCPs of all 300 scenarios are displayed, with

the reference scenario highlighted. Results are distinguished between capacity calculation only (blue) and capacity calculation with validation (red).

Capacity calculation: For low minRAM values (0 – 10%), the distribution of MCP deviations exhibits non-zero medians and spreads, indicating that forecast uncertainty affects the market outcome. Different forecast scenarios lead to different shapes and sizes of the flow-based domain and, consequently, to different MCPs. As minRAM increases, both the median and the spread of deviations decrease, and from 20% onwards the MCP deviations are zero. This shows that with larger minRAM, capacity calculation becomes insensitive to forecast uncertainty, as the enlarged flow-based domain fully absorbs the variations. The effect is illustrated in Fig. 4.3: in the 0% case, the flow-based domain varies across scenarios, resulting in different MCPs, whereas in the 40% case the domains are identical across scenarios and yield the same MCP.

Validation: For minRAM values of 0 – 20%, the results with and without validation are nearly identical, with differences limited to a few outliers. In these cases, the validated domain does not alter the MCP compared to the initial capacity calculation, as IVAs are rarely applied. For higher minRAM values (30 – 50%), however, the inclusion of validation increases both the median and spread of MCP deviations. At these levels, validation actively applies IVAs, thereby limiting the market domain and resulting in different MCPs. The number and magnitude of applied IVAs depend on the renewable forecast. The bottom right panel of Fig. 4.3 shows the domains for the 40% minRAM case with validation: in some scenarios, the domain remains unchanged compared to capacity calculation alone, while in others, the domain size is reduced and the MCP shifts accordingly.

The results show how outcomes of the individual subprocesses, influenced by forecast uncertainty, affect the market result. In capacity calculation, the propagation of renewable uncertainty is limited to very low minRAM values. Once minRAM adjustments are applied, variations in the forecasts are absorbed by enlarged domains and the market results converge to the same outcome. Validation, in contrast, is applied after minRAM adjustment and therefore impacts the market result independent of minRAM adjustments.

From this observation follows the implication for robust modelling: Robustness is most effective when implemented in the subprocess where uncertainty has the strongest impact. Since the effect of uncertainty in capacity calculation is largely neutralised by minRAM, adding robustness at this stage has limited value. Validation, however, directly reflects the influence of forecast uncertainty and a uncertainty-aware implementation can therefore effectively increase robustness.

Fig. 4.2.: Distribution of MCP deviations under renewable forecast uncertainty for different values of minRAM. Results are shown for capacity calculation only (blue) and capacity calculation with validation (red). The deviations are measured as Euclidean distance to the reference MCP.

Fig. 4.3.: Flow-based domains and resulting MCPs for 300 forecast scenarios under 0% (left) and 40% (right) minRAM. Top panels show results for capacity calculation only; bottom panels include validation. The reference scenario is highlighted.

4.1.2 Single-Scenario Analysis: Deterministic and Probabilistic Approaches

In this subsection, the modelling framework is applied to a single illustrative scenario. The aim is twofold: first, to demonstrate the necessity of modelling the validation step by comparing capacity calculation outcomes with and without validation under deterministic conditions; and second, to introduce forecast uncertainty and compare deterministic and probabilistic approaches to handling it. To this end, five cases are analysed (Table 4.4). Cases 1–3 are deterministic and highlight the effect of minRAM and the role of validation. Cases 4 and 5 introduce renewable forecast uncertainty and compare deterministic validation with a probabilistic alternative.

In Case 1, capacity calculation, market coupling, and redispatch are modelled in sequence, but minRAM is set to 0% and the validation step is omitted. In Case 2, minRAM is set to 50% of each line’s maximum capacity, with otherwise identical settings. Case 3 extends this setup by introducing the validation sub-process into the modelling chain. All three runs are performed under *deterministic* conditions, meaning that no uncertainty is introduced and the calculations are carried out under perfect foresight of renewable availability at D-0.

Building on these, Cases 4 and 5 introduce forecast uncertainty. Here, photovoltaic forecasts are subject to error ($\sigma_{PV} = 0.2$), with the forecast error realised at $t = D-0$. This means that the redispatch sub-process uses updated values for PV availability, while the earlier steps rely on imperfect forecasts. Case 4 mirrors the settings of Case 3 but adds uncertainty. Case 5 replaces deterministic validation with its probabilistic counterpart. The risk tolerance ϵ is set to 5% [49, 48]. For all cases, the FRM is set to 0%. The model settings are summarised in Table 4.4.

Tab. 4.4.: Model settings for single-scenario analysis

Setting	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4	Case 5
Std. Deviation σ_{PV}	0	0	0	0.2	0.2
minRAM	0%	50%	50%	50%	50%
Validation (deterministic)	False	False	True	True	False
Validation (probabilistic)	False	False	False	False	True
Vertex selection θ_{max}	-	-	40°	40°	40°

The resulting domains for the five cases are shown in Figure 4.4, while line flows after each stage on the critical line L2 are displayed in Fig. 4.5. The axes in Fig. 4.4 define the exchange volumes between zones Z1–Z2 and Z1–Z3. The net position forecast (NPF), is marked with a black square, while the market clearing point (MCP) is indicated by a red circle. Each line corresponds to a CNEC that limits the domain, and the final flow-based domain available to the market is highlighted in black. Coloured areas illustrate whether

points in the domain are operationally secure (green), not reachable due to generation constraints (yellow), or operationally insecure (red). They were obtained by validating individual net position combinations that satisfy the balance constraint and projecting them to the shown domain visualization². Note, that these areas are not part of the process model but calculated afterwards to help visualize where the market is able to clear and where it results in unsolvable congestions.

Figure 4.4a shows the initial flow-based domain (Case 1). Exchanges from Zone 1 to Zone 3 are constrained, while transfers between Zone 1 and Zone 2 are less restricted. The MCP and NPF coincide in a net import position of Zone 1 and export positions for Zones 2 and 3. All positions within the market domain are secure or not reachable due to generation limits. As Figure 4.5 shows, the flow on Line 2 resulting from market coupling in Case 1 exceeds the physical limit (30 MW), but the congestion can be resolved in the redispatch process.

In Case 2 (Fig. 4.4b), the introduction of minRAM enlarges the flow-based domain. This enlargement extends the market domain into operationally insecure regions, and the MCP shifts to an insecure position with increased exports from Zone 2. As shown in Figure 4.5, redispatch is unable to reduce the flow on Line 2 below its capacity, leaving residual congestion.

In Case 3 (Fig. 4.4c), validation reduces the market domain by excluding the insecure positions introduced by minRAM. The MCP is restored to a secure outcome, and, as shown in Figure 4.5, redispatch again succeeds in resolving the overload on Line 2. This sequence confirms that validation is necessary to guarantee feasibility once minRAM is applied.

Figure 4.4d shows the results when PV forecast uncertainty is introduced. The realised error in PV availability for Cases 4 and 5 can be seen in Table 4.5. In the analysed scenario both PV plants have higher forecasts for D-2 and D-1 than available on D-0. The domain and resulting MCP appear identical to Case 3. This is expected, as deterministic validation relies on D-2 forecasts, which remain unchanged. The updated RES availability at D-0 is reflected in the validated background areas: the share of operationally insecure positions increases, while the share of operationally secure position decreases. The MCP position that was operationally secure in Case 3 becomes operationally insecure in Case 4. Consequently, the overload on Line 2 is not resolved in redispatch.

²A net position vector can be validated with the described two stage implementation. Instead of maximizing the scaling factor a , it is checked if the constraints Eq. 3.23b-3.23h can be fulfilled in the given net position combination (green). If generation and load constraints fail, the point is not reachable (yellow), if line constraints fail, it is not operationally secure (red). The net position vector is projected to the exchange visualisation as described in 3.3.6 and keeping exchanges Z2-Z3 zero. A detailed description of the process is described in the appendix A.1.

(a) Case 1: Initial flow-based domain

(b) Case 2: minRAM enlarged flow-based domain

(c) Case 3: Flow-based domain with validation

(d) Case 4: Flow-based domain with validation under uncertainty

(e) Case 5: Flow-based domain with probabilistic validation

Fig. 4.4.: Flow-based domain representations for exchanges between zones 1–2 and zones 1–3 in the 3-zone/4-node network. Case 1 (a): base computation, Case 2 (b): including minRAM enlargement, Case 3 (c): including deterministic validation, Case 4 (d): deterministic validation under uncertainty, Case 5 (e): probabilistic validation.

Fig. 4.5.: Line 2 flows in the three subprocess stages (basecase, market coupling, redispatch) for Cases 1–5. The maximum capacity is 30 MW.

Name	Node	\bar{p}	$p^{\max,pu}$	σ	\hat{p}^{D-2}	\hat{p}^{D-1}	\hat{p}^{D-0}
Wind2 ^{ctrl}	N2	210.0	0.8	0.0	168.0	168.0	168.0
Wind2 ^{unc}	N2	90.0	0.8	0.0	72.0	72.0	72.0
PV3 ^{ctrl}	N3	25.0	0.7	0.0	17.5	17.5	17.5
PV3 ^{unc}	N3	25.0	0.7	0.2	17.5	17.5	9.5
PV4 ^{ctrl}	N4	50.0	0.7	0.0	35.0	35.0	35.0
PV4 ^{unc}	N4	50.0	0.7	0.2	35.0	35.0	30.7

Tab. 4.5.: RES parameters for Cases 4 and 5 in the analysed scenario.

Figure 4.4e shows the results with probabilistic validation via chance-constraints. The resulting market domain is the most restrictive of all cases, but only secure or unreachable positions are included inside the domain. The MCP lies in a secure region, and Figure 4.5 demonstrates that redispatch can fully resolve the congestion on Line 2.

The single-scenario analysis highlights two key insights. First, Cases 1–3 show that minRAM adjustments can compromise operational security and that the introduction of the validation process is required to exclude insecure outcomes. Second, Cases 4–5 demonstrate that the deterministic validation approach can be insufficient under forecast uncertainty, as it fails to prevent an operationally insecure market outcome, whereas the probabilistic validation successfully restores security by enforcing robustness, though with a more restrictive domain.

The next section expands on this analysis by modelling multiple scenarios of uncertainty realisation and its impact on system costs, redispatch needs and operational security.

4.1.3 Deterministic and Probabilistic Validation for Multiple Scenarios

The single-scenario analysis in the previous section illustrated that deterministic validation can fail to prevent infeasible market outcomes under renewable forecast uncertainty, while probabilistic validation ensures robustness at the cost of a more restrictive domain. To extend this finding, the same setup is now analysed for a set of 600 scenarios, in which forecast errors are introduced at both D-1 and D-0. The same error realisation is applied at both time steps. Three cases are compared: a model without validation, a model with deterministic validation, and a model with probabilistic validation via chance-constraints.

The results are summarised in the following. Figure 4.6 shows the distribution of total system costs across scenarios and marks those with ROs resulting in infeasible redispatch solutions, Figure 4.7 decomposes total costs into market and redispatch components and Table 4.6 reports the mean values of the key indicators for system costs, redispatch needs and operational security.

Fig. 4.6.: Distribution of total system costs across 600 scenarios for the three cases: no validation, deterministic validation, and probabilistic validation. Scenarios with remaining overloads are marked.

Without validation, the total system costs are lowest. However, remaining overloads cannot be prevented and every scenario results in an infeasible redispatch solution.

Fig. 4.7.: Decomposition of system costs into day-ahead market costs and redispatch costs for the three cases.

Tab. 4.6.: Comparison of key results across the three cases.

Metric	No Val.	Det. Val.	Prob. Val.
Mean Total System Cost [k€]	16.04	24.36	26.59
Mean Market Cost [k€]	7.43	13.07	16.71
Mean Redispatch Cost [k€]	8.61	11.28	9.88
Mean Redispatch Volume [MW]	50.65	66.38	58.14
Share of Scenarios with ROs	100%	51%	1%
Mean Size of ROs [MW]	17.80	2.96	1.00
Max Size of ROs [MW]	28.23	10.56	3.12

Introducing deterministic validation increases total costs and decreases the share of scenarios with overloads from 100% to 51%. Probabilistic validation yields the highest market cost, while infeasible scenarios reduce to 1%. Splitting the system costs into day-ahead market costs and redispatch shows that while market costs increase from one case to the next, redispatch costs are slightly lower for the probabilistic process compared to the deterministic one.

Taken together, these results highlight a clear trade-off between efficiency and operational security. The observed trade-off between higher system costs and improved security motivates the analysis in the next section, where the role of the risk tolerance parameter ε in the probabilistic validation is examined.

Fig. 4.8.: Sensitivity of system outcomes to risk tolerance ϵ . Lower ϵ increases system costs while reducing the frequency and size of remaining overloads. The dashed line marks deterministic validation, which corresponds approximately to $\epsilon = 0.5$ under the assumed normal distribution of forecast errors.

4.1.4 Sensitivity Analysis of Risk Tolerance

In the probabilistic validation, the parameter ϵ defines the tolerated risk level. It specifies the probability that a constraint is violated at a validated vertex of the flow-based domain (see section 3.4.4). Smaller values of ϵ therefore enforce greater capacity reductions, while larger values permit more risk-taking and less validation adjustments.

To further investigate the properties of the probabilistic validation, a sensitivity analysis of the risk tolerance parameter ϵ is performed. In the experiment, ϵ is varied between 0.01 and 1, and the system is evaluated over 100 forecast scenarios (realizations at D-2 and D-1). Three key metrics are recorded: total system cost, the share of scenarios with remaining overloads, and the mean size of remaining overloads.

Figure 4.8 shows that total system cost increases monotonically with decreasing ϵ . For intermediate values of ϵ , the relationship is close to linear, while for extreme values the cost grows more steeply, resembling an exponential increase.

The fraction of scenarios with remaining overloads decreases almost linearly with smaller ϵ . However, the relationship is not exact. For $\epsilon < 0.35$ the model appears conservative (fewer infeasible cases than the nominal level), while for $\epsilon > 0.35$ the realized infeasibility is slightly above the nominal probability. This is because the risk tolerance in the applied formulation does not directly prescribe the overall percentage of infeasible market outcomes. Instead, ϵ sets the probability that a given validated vertex of the flow-based domain is feasible under uncertainty. In the small test system, the market

tends to clear near the validated vertices (see Fig 4.4), so the realized share of infeasible outcomes reflects ε almost directly.

The mean size of remaining overloads decreases as ε becomes smaller, confirming that violations not only occur less often but also tend to be less severe.

Deterministic validation produces results that correspond closely to $\varepsilon \approx 0.5$. This mapping is not universal but can be explained by the distributional assumptions: under normally distributed forecast errors, validating against a single deterministic outcome implicitly accepts about a 50% risk level.

Overall, the analysis highlights the fundamental trade-off: smaller values of ε improve operational security at the cost of higher ex-ante expenditures, while larger ε values reduce costs but allow more frequent and larger remaining congestions after redispatch. The choice of ε therefore provides a direct tuning parameter to balance conservatism and efficiency in probabilistic validation.

4.2 Discussion of the 4-Node Case Study

The 4-node test system serves as a transparent environment to validate the `munacco` framework and to illustrate how renewable uncertainty propagates through the CACM subprocesses. While the quantitative results cannot be generalised to realistic grids, the case provides several important insights into model behaviour, subprocess sensitivity, and the role of validation. It thereby directly addresses elements of RQ1 and RQ3.

The small network allows each subprocess to be traced in detail, from capacity calculation to redispatch. Expected behaviours are reproduced: `minRAM` enlarges the flow-based domain [24, 43], validation can restrict it in case of endangered operational security [26], and redispatch resolves remaining violations where possible [22]. The single scenario case study thus demonstrates that the workflow and data structures of `munacco` function as intended and that results are consistent with intuition and earlier studies on flow-based market coupling.

A key finding with respect to RQ1 is that forecast uncertainty affects subprocesses unevenly. Capacity calculation becomes largely insensitive once `minRAM` enlargements are applied: the expanded domains absorb forecast variations and yield identical market outcomes. Validation, in contrast, directly translates forecast deviations into adjustments of the feasible domain. Validation thus emerges as the most effective subprocess for implementing robustness against uncertainty. It must be noted, however, that this conclusion rests on two modelling assumptions: the active constraint, being the CNEC

limiting the market, must be sensitive to renewable injections, and it must also be affected by minRAM adjustments. In the stylised example, Line 2 fulfils both of these conditions: it is directly influenced by RES injections at Nodes 2 and 3 and subject to minRAM adjustments, since zone-internal flows already occupy more than 30% of its capacity in the basecase. The demand and generation profiles were deliberately chosen to showcase this effect. Nonetheless, the principle generalises: whenever active CNECs combine RES sensitivity with minRAM adjustments, forecast errors will primarily manifest in validation. If the first condition does not hold — i.e., the active CNEC is not sensitive to renewable injections — forecast uncertainty has little or no effect on outcomes. If the second condition does not hold — i.e., the CNEC is unaffected by minRAM — then both capacity calculation and validation propagate forecast errors in the same way, corresponding to a 0% minRAM case. In either case, however, the relative role of validation in mediating robustness remains central. This mechanism is not restricted to the stylised case but reflects a structural feature of the sequential order in the CACM chain.

The single- and multi-scenario analyses address RQ2 and RQ3 by comparing deterministic and probabilistic validation. Deterministic validation is only partially effective under renewable forecast uncertainty. In the single-scenario case, it relied on the D-2 forecast and therefore failed to prevent infeasible outcomes once forecast errors materialised at D-0. In the multi-scenario case, it reduced the share of infeasible outcomes compared to the no-validation benchmark (from 100% to 51%) but still left a substantial number of residual overloads. This partial effectiveness reflects a structural limitation of deterministic methods: by relying on point forecasts, they cannot provide guarantees across a distribution of outcomes.

Probabilistic validation via chance-constraints overcomes this limitation by embedding risk preferences directly into the decision framework. In the single-scenario experiment, it successfully excluded infeasible outcomes that deterministic validation allowed. Across multiple scenarios, it reduced the share of infeasible outcomes from 51% to 1%. These findings are consistent with the broader literature on chance-constrained optimization, which provides tractable ways to incorporate probabilistic security margins into power system operation [11, 47]. The sensitivity analysis of the risk tolerance parameter ε further clarified the mechanism: smaller values of ε improved security at the cost of higher system expenditures, whereas larger values reduced costs but increased risk. This trade-off between cost and security is well established in the literature on chance-constrained optimal power flow [59, 48]. It has to be noted, however, that remaining congestions after redispatch are not penalized in the cost analysis. In practice, TSOs would have to revert to emergency procedures to ensure system security (see section 2.1.4), which would cause additional system costs.

The novelty of this study lies in applying this framework to CACM validation, where probabilistic margins had not previously been integrated into the flow-based market coupling

chain. Deterministic validation corresponded approximately to $\varepsilon \approx 0.5$ under normally distributed forecast errors, situating it as a mid-level risk benchmark. These findings confirm that probabilistic approaches can systematically balance operational security, redispatch needs, and market efficiency, whereas deterministic methods cannot.

The stylised 4-node system has inherent limitations. It was deliberately designed as a toy example to highlight the research objective: one critical line, limited redispatch potential on conventional generators, and demand–generation profiles were chosen to make the effect of forecast uncertainty visible. As such, it represents only one possible situation in a very simplified network topology. With its simple zone structure and absence of meshed flows, and heterogeneous resources, it cannot reproduce the complexity of realistic grids. The absolute cost levels and redispatch volumes are therefore not representative of real systems. Nevertheless, the case fulfills its role as a sandbox: it validates the munacco workflow, clarifies the propagation of uncertainty across subprocesses, and demonstrates the value of probabilistic validation.

In summary, the 4-node experiments establish three central insights:

- Validation is the subprocess where renewable forecast uncertainty needs to be addressed.
- Deterministic validation fails to provide sufficient robustness under uncertainty.
- Probabilistic validation enables robust operation, with ε offering a direct parameter to balance cost and security.

These interim conclusions motivate the transition to the 50-node case. Unlike the stylised 4-node system, the larger network is not handcrafted to showcase one effect, but is derived from a model representation of Europe’s transmission system network with hourly data. This allows the same mechanisms to be tested in a more complex and diverse environment that better reflects the variability of real-world system conditions.

4.3 Large Scale Application on a 50-Node PyPSA-Eur Network

4.3.1 Dataset and Preprocessing

The large-scale case study is based on the open-source European sector-coupled energy system model PyPSA-Eur [68], which provides a high-resolution representation of the European transmission grid, electricity demand, and renewable generation potentials. The framework is implemented on top of the PyPSA toolbox [54], which can be applied for operational as well as expansion studies. The underlying transmission grid data is derived from OpenStreetMap [69], while renewable generation potentials are obtained from the ERA5 reanalysis dataset [70] and the SARA3 satellite product [71]. For temporal consistency, the reference year 2013 is used throughout, following [72]. All data retrieval, harmonisation, and preprocessing steps are automated within the PyPSA-Eur Snakemake workflow [73].

For the purpose of this study, the model was restricted to the Central Western Europe (CWE) region (Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, Luxembourg, and the Netherlands) [21]. The dataset was simplified by excluding storage technologies, high voltage direct current (HVDC) interconnections, and all sector-coupling components. To obtain a computationally tractable representation, the network was clustered to 50 nodes using the k-means-based spatial aggregation implemented in PyPSA-Eur³ [68]. Following current practice, Germany and Luxembourg were considered as a single bidding zone [74]. To approximate $N - 1$ security, transmission line capacities were derated to 70% of their nominal dynamic rating, in line with [75]. The resulting network topology with maximum line capacities is shown in Fig. 4.9.

Two network variants were analysed. The first, denoted *low RES*, reflects current installed generation capacities derived directly from the clustered base network. The second, denoted *high RES*, was obtained by optimising generation capacities in the clustered network using the expansion module of PyPSA [54], while keeping the transmission topology fixed. In the low RES case, renewable energy sources constitute 51% of total installed capacity, compared to 67% in the high RES case. Figure 4.10 shows the installed capacities per zone and technology for both variants.

A preprocessing step was required to ensure feasibility under the separation of renewable units into controllable and uncertain shares (cf. Section 3.2). Without adjustment, cases can occur where uncontrollable renewable output exceeds local demand, rendering the nodal balance infeasible. To avoid such situations, nodal demand was adjusted hourly

³The corresponding config.yaml file for the Snakemake workflow is available on zenodo [65].

Fig. 4.9.: Topology of 50-Node network generated with PyPSA-Eur with zones and maximum line capacity indicated by color.

Fig. 4.10.: Installed capacities per zone and carrier for two cases: low RES and high RES.

according to two rules: (i) the maximum demand in each zone was capped at the sum of installed generation capacities, and (ii) the minimum demand was set equal to the sum of uncontrollable renewable generation. These adjustments slightly modified the annual demand time series while preserving its statistical structure. In the low RES case, total annual demand increased by 5.23%. In the high RES case, adjustments were minor: demand was increased in 9% of hours (0.14% of annual demand, primarily in Austria) and reduced in 35% of hours (0.7% of annual demand). Overall, the adjustments ensured nodal feasibility across all scenarios in the low RES case and 99.3% of scenarios in the high RES case.

4.3.2 Model Setup

The simulations were conducted using the `munacco` framework as described in Chapter 3. To capture the variability of renewable generation while maintaining computational tractability, the hourly dataset of the reference year was downsampled to every fifth hour, resulting in $n = 1752$ time steps. For each time step, 100 uncertainty scenarios were generated by perturbing the availability of renewable generators with independent normally distributed forecast errors of standard deviation $\sigma = 0.2$ relative to installed capacity [49]. No correlation between renewable units was assumed. The forecast errors were set to materialise only at the redispatch stage (D-0), thereby representing a setting where capacity calculation and market coupling rely on the same forecasts and deviations appear only at real-time operation.

The minRAM requirement was set to 70% [13], while the FRM was set to 0%. During validation, vertices were selected from the flow-based domain using an angular threshold of 40° relative to the forecasted net position, with a minimum of six and a maximum of ten vertices per time step. The probabilistic validation employed a risk level of $\varepsilon = 0.05$, consistent with the small-scale case study in Section 4.1.

Participation factors α_g were applied to model the response of conventional generators to forecast errors. To reduce computational burden, the participation factors were pre-calculated ex ante based on installed capacity shares rather than optimised endogenously and only apply to units with generation capacity larger than 800 MW.

Each of the 1752 time steps was simulated under both deterministic and probabilistic validation, resulting in a total of 350,400 model runs per network variant. This paired design allows direct comparison of deterministic and uncertainty-aware approaches under otherwise identical conditions.

4.3.3 Results

The large-scale simulations extend the insights from the stylised 4-node case to a more realistic 50-node representation of the Central Western European grid. Results are reported for both the low and high RES variants, comparing deterministic and probabilistic validation.

Table 4.7 summarises operational security and cost outcomes. In the low RES case, deterministic validation already achieved near-complete robustness: remaining overloads occurred in only 0.17% of hours and affected more than 5% of scenarios in just 0.11% of hours. Probabilistic validation eliminated these residual violations entirely. In the high RES case, the effect of forecast uncertainty was considerably stronger. Deterministic

validation left overloads in 20.9% of hours, and in 9.4% of hours more than 5% of scenarios were infeasible. Under probabilistic validation, these shares were reduced to 5.3% and 2.3%, respectively. These figures demonstrate that the robustness gap between deterministic and probabilistic validation widens as renewable penetration increases.

Tab. 4.7.: Operational security and cost outcomes for the low and high RES cases under deterministic (Det.) and probabilistic (Prob.) validation. Costs are given in million EUR.

Metric	Low RES		High RES	
	Det.	Prob.	Det.	Prob.
Operational Security				
Scenarios with remaining overloads	85	0	3983	703
Hours with remaining overloads	3	0	363	92
Share of hours with RO in ≥ 1 scenario [%]	0.17	0.00	20.87	5.29
Share of hours with RO in > 5 scenarios [%]	0.11	0.00	9.37	2.30
Costs				
Mean Market Costs [mio. EUR]	3.726	3.913	2.292	2.732
Mean Redispatch Costs [mio. EUR]	0.604	0.412	0.903	0.531
Mean Total System Costs [mio. EUR]	4.329	4.325	3.195	3.263
Mean Total System Costs w LS [mio. EUR]	4.329	4.325	3.509	3.309

Fig. 4.11.: Distribution of day-ahead market costs, redispatch costs, and total system costs across all scenarios for the low and high RES cases under deterministic (Det.) and probabilistic (Prob.) validation.

Average cost outcomes mirror this pattern. All reported cost values represent averages across all scenarios and hours, i.e. expected system costs under each RES and validation

case. In both RES cases, probabilistic validation increased day-ahead market costs relative to deterministic validation, while reducing redispatch expenditures. In the low RES case, total system costs were nearly identical (4.329 vs. 4.325 million EUR). In the high RES case, probabilistic validation increased total costs slightly (3.195 vs. 3.263 million EUR), but with a notable shift from ex-post redispatch to ex-ante market adjustment. When valuing remaining overloads as equivalent load shedding (LS) at a Value of Lost Load (VoLL) of €20,000/MWh, the high RES case shows a clear difference: deterministic validation leads to substantially higher total costs with load shedding (3.509 vs. 3.309 million EUR). This reflects that unresolved overloads in the deterministic case would require more corrective measures, whereas probabilistic validation reduces both the frequency of overloads and their associated costs. In the low RES case, overloads were negligible, so total costs with load shedding remain unchanged.

The distributional perspective in Fig. 4.11 highlights this cost reallocation. Probabilistic validation reduces the spread and frequency of high redispatch costs, effectively suppressing extreme outliers. At the same time, it increases market expenditures, resulting in a more predictable but more conservative allocation of transmission capacity.

Overall, the 50-node simulations reproduce the main mechanism identified in the 4-node case: deterministic validation leaves residual risks under renewable uncertainty, while probabilistic validation reduces infeasibilities and redispatch variance at the expense of higher day-ahead market costs. Total system costs remain broadly stable, but the balance shifts from remedial redispatch to preventive action.

Discussion and Limitations

5.1 Synthesis of Results

The results of this thesis demonstrate that renewable forecast uncertainty has a measurable and systematic effect on the coordinated capacity allocation and congestion management (CACM) process chain. When uncertainty is modelled explicitly, additional overloads arise, some of which cannot be resolved through redispatch and therefore pose a risk to operational security. The 4-node case study showed that the validation step is the subprocess where robustness can most effectively be introduced, since capacity calculation becomes largely insensitive once minRAM enlargements are applied. Deterministic approaches, by relying on point forecasts, do not account for uncertainty and can therefore lead to infeasible redispatch situations. By contrast, probabilistic validation reduces the risk of such outcomes substantially by restricting the margins available for cross-zonal exchanges in the day-ahead market.

The comparison of the two case studies confirms that this mechanism persists under more complex and realistic conditions. The stylised 4-node system, deliberately designed around a single critical line and with limited redispatch flexibility, provided analytical clarity in tracing how forecast errors propagate through the process chain. The 50-node network, not tailored to a single effect, was derived from realistic grid data and hourly demand and generation patterns. Despite its greater complexity and more diverse congestion patterns, the larger case confirmed the same fundamental result: deterministic validation leaves residual operational risks under uncertainty, whereas probabilistic formulations provide substantially greater robustness. Additionally, probabilistic validation increases day-ahead market costs, but these higher ex-ante expenditures are accompanied by lower redispatch costs ex post.

These results are consistent with findings in the literature. The observed trade-off between larger market capacities and higher redispatch needs echoes the findings of [24], while the reduction in redispatch costs under probabilistic approaches aligns with [11]. The persistence of congestions due to forecast errors supports the observations of [51]. At the same time, this thesis goes further by explicitly assessing operational security across the entire CACM chain. This contrasts in particular with the conclusions of [50], who found that forecast errors have little effect on the FBMC process. Their analysis did not

consider operational security, which explains the divergence in findings and underlines the importance of including this dimension explicitly.

5.2 Broader Interpretation

The results highlight that robustness, as implemented in this study, can be understood as a systematic reduction of cross-zonal transmission capacities. In principle, such reductions could be achieved by several methods. For instance, [11] propose probabilistic security margins (FRM) applied during capacity calculation. However, the effectiveness of such methods depends critically on the treatment of minRAM. If minRAM is implemented as a fixed percentage of the maximum line capacity F_{\max} , the additional robustness gained through probabilistic margins may be neutralised. If, by contrast, minRAM is defined relative to $F_{\max} - \text{FRM}$, robustness can enter in the capacity calculation process. The key contribution of this thesis is to show that robustness can also be operationalised explicitly at the validation stage, which has so far been absent in existing modelling frameworks.

5.3 Limitations of the Study

Despite these contributions, several limitations must be acknowledged. The scope of the analysis is restricted to the day-ahead timeframe. In real-world operation, an additional intraday process repeats the sequence of capacity calculation, validation, and market coupling, thereby allowing adjustments as more accurate forecasts become available [18]. Excluding this process means that the results cannot capture the full flexibility available to system operators.

The modelling framework itself relies on a number of simplifying assumptions that are common in system-level studies but nevertheless limit realism. Power flows are represented by a linear approximation without losses. Demand is assumed fixed and inelastic, strategic bidding behaviour is excluded, and neither storage technologies nor HVDC interconnectors are represented. Ramping constraints for generators are also neglected, which may overstate redispatch flexibility [76].

Further limitations arise from the design and implementation of the case studies. The 4-node example was deliberately hand-crafted to illustrate one mechanism and cannot be generalised. The 50-node network, while derived from PyPSA-Eur, is clustered and aggregated, and not calibrated to real-world statistics. Such aggregation can lead to unrealistic simplifications, for example by summing parallel interconnectors or combining renewable and conventional generators at a single node, which reduces the visibility of localised uncertainty impacts. Several computationally motivated adjustments were also

introduced to ensure tractable runtimes, including slack variables, ex ante fixed participation factors α , and penalty costs in multi-objective optimisation. These adjustments preserve high-level insights but may bias detailed outcomes. Redispatch was modelled in a single optimisation step across the entire network, which introduces an optimistic bias compared to practical zonal redispatch, while the exclusion of cross-zonal redispatch introduces a conservative bias. In addition, all conventional plants, including nuclear units, were assumed redispatchable, which overstates operational flexibility. The resolution of the 50-node network is still relatively coarse, likely underestimating congestion as highlighted by [77].

The treatment of renewable uncertainty also involves simplifications. Renewable generation was split into controllable and uncontrollable components, which required adjusting demand time series to ensure feasibility. This introduced artificial rigidity and excluded extreme events where renewable availability falls below the controllable share. Forecast errors were represented as independent normal distributions with fixed variance, ignoring spatial and temporal correlations. Finally, cost data were not calibrated to real-world values, so redispatch and market expenditures should be interpreted qualitatively, highlighting trends and trade-offs rather than providing numerical policy guidance.

Taken together, these limitations imply that the results of this thesis should be viewed as qualitative rather than quantitative. The findings robustly demonstrate mechanisms and trade-offs, particularly the role of validation under uncertainty, but cannot be used to predict exact operational costs or redispatch volumes. Future work could address these limitations by extending the scope to intraday processes, refining redispatch modelling at the zonal level, and incorporating correlated forecast errors in higher-resolution networks.

5.4 Practical Implications

Despite these limitations, the results offer practical insights. The simulations clearly show that renewable forecast uncertainty affects the CACM process and that failing to address it can jeopardise operational security. Validation emerges as an effective subprocess for implementing robustness, even under existing minRAM requirements. The probabilistic approach tested in this study is one possible means of achieving this, but not the only one. Other methods, such as probabilistic security margins at the capacity calculation stage, may also be viable if carefully integrated with existing regulations.

At the same time, it must be emphasised that the modelling framework developed here is primarily suitable for assessing methodological approaches. Real-world processes have higher dimensionality, stricter time constraints, and additional operational layers that

cannot be fully captured in this study. Hence, the framework should be viewed as a tool for exploring and comparing uncertainty-aware methods rather than a direct blueprint for implementation.

Finally, the mechanism by which robustness is achieved in the model—through stricter margins on cross-zonal exchanges prior to market coupling—highlights a central policy challenge. While the principle is clear, the question of how such margins could be operationalised in practice, within the institutional and regulatory context of European market coupling, remains open. Addressing this issue will be crucial for translating modelling insights into actionable policy and operational measures.

5.5 Future Work

Several paths for future research follow from these findings. Extending the framework to larger and higher-resolution networks would improve the realism of congestion patterns. Modelling redispatch at the zonal level, rather than across the whole system, would yield more accurate estimates of flexibility. Incorporating intraday processes would better capture the iterative nature of operational planning. The uncertainty model could be refined by introducing correlated renewable forecast errors, better reflecting spatial covariance. Finally, calibrating cost parameters to realistic values would allow policy-relevant assessments of efficiency and security impacts.

Conclusions and Outlook

This thesis analysed how renewable forecast uncertainty propagates through the coordinated capacity allocation and congestion management (CACM) process chain, and how robustness can be incorporated. Two case studies were applied: a stylised 4-node system to isolate key mechanisms and a 50-node PyPSA-Eur network to test their persistence under more realistic conditions.

The results show that forecast uncertainty systematically affects CACM outcomes, leading to an increase of line overloads. Deterministic validation reduces but does not eliminate these, leaving residual overloads that redispatch cannot fully resolve. Probabilistic validation, by contrast, substantially improves robustness by imposing stricter margins for cross-zonal exchanges. This shifts costs from ex post redispatch to ex ante market allocation, limiting the impact on total system costs. Across both cases, the validation step emerged as the critical subprocess where uncertainty materialises and robustness can most effectively be introduced.

The main contribution lies in explicitly modelling the validation step, which has been largely neglected in prior studies, and in demonstrating that probabilistic methods can feasibly complement current deterministic practice. By combining stylised and large-scale networks, the thesis further shows that these mechanisms hold across different levels of complexity.

These conclusions must be interpreted in light of simplifications. The scope was limited to the day-ahead timeframe, excluding intraday adjustments. Standard modelling assumptions such as DC power flow, fixed demand, and the omission of storage, HVDC lines, and ramping constraints reduce realism. The 50-node network was aggregated and not statistically calibrated, redispatch was simplified, and renewable uncertainty was modelled with independent Gaussian errors. Costs were not calibrated to real-world values. The results should therefore be read as qualitative insights into mechanisms and trade-offs rather than quantitative forecasts.

Future work should extend the analysis to intraday processes, refine redispatch modelling at the zonal level, and incorporate spatially and temporally correlated forecast errors in higher-resolution networks. Alternative robustness concepts, such as probabilistic security

margins in capacity calculation, also warrant investigation, as does their integration into European CACM regulation.

In sum, this thesis demonstrates that renewable forecast uncertainty cannot be ignored in the CACM process and that robustness can be effectively introduced through probabilistic validation. This enhances operational security, highlighting the importance of uncertainty-aware methods for the reliable and efficient operation of a renewable-dominated European electricity system.

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Appendix

A.1 Visualisation of validated exchange positions

This appendix describes the procedure used to generate the coloured areas in the flow-based domains shown in Fig. 4.4 (Section 4.1.2). These visual elements are added after the model run and serve to illustrate how different subprocesses shape the domain and why certain regions of the exchange space are feasible or infeasible. The procedure is summarised in Fig. A.1.

First, a grid of zonal net position combinations is constructed under the feasibility condition

$$\sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} NP_z = 0.$$

Each combination corresponds to a point in the multidimensional space spanned by the zonal net positions.

Second, each point is validated individually using the two-stage validation procedure described in Section 3.4.2. Instead of maximising the scaling factor a , the problem is solved as a feasibility check of constraints (3.23b)–(3.23h). Points that fail generation or load constraints are marked as *not reachable* (yellow). Points that satisfy these constraints but violate line limits are marked as *not secure* (red). Remaining points, which admit a feasible nodal solution including line constraints, are marked as *secure* (green).

Finally, the validated grid is projected from net position space to the exchange space in which flow-based domains are visualised. Zonal exchanges are computed using the method of Section 3.3.6. Since only two exchanges can be shown in a 2D plot, all others must be fixed. In the example of Fig. A.1, the exchanges between zones 1–2 and 1–3 are displayed, while exchange 2–3 is fixed to zero. This projection has the effect that an initially equidistant grid in net position space can appear skewed when displayed in exchange space.

Fig. A.1.: Process of computing validated areas in flow-based domain plots.

Colophon

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Eigenständigkeitserklärung

Hiermit versichere ich, dass ich die vorliegende Arbeit eigenständig ohne Hilfe Dritter und ausschließlich unter Verwendung der aufgeführten Quellen und Hilfsmittel angefertigt habe. Alle Stellen die den benutzten Quellen und Hilfsmitteln unverändert oder sinngemäß entnommen sind, habe ich als solche kenntlich gemacht.

Sofern KI-Tools verwendet wurden, habe ich Produktnamen, Hersteller, die jeweils verwendete Softwareversion und die Art der Nutzung (z.B. sprachliche Überprüfung und Verbesserung der Texte, systematische Recherche) benannt. Während der Erstellung dieser Arbeit habe ich Chat-GPT 5 von OpenAI und DeepL Write verwendet, um die Sprache und Lesbarkeit zu verbessern. Ich verantworte die Auswahl, die Übernahme und sämtliche Ergebnisse des von mir verwendeten KI-generierten Outputs vollumfänglich selbst.

Die Satzung zur Sicherung guter wissenschaftlicher Praxis an der TU Berlin vom 15. Februar 2023 [78] habe ich zur Kenntnis genommen.

Ich erkläre weiterhin, dass ich die Arbeit in gleicher oder ähnlicher Form noch keiner anderen Prüfungsbehörde vorgelegt habe.

Berlin, September 30, 2025

Maximilian Voigt

